

Deliverable 4.3

Improving policy development processes and Decentralised Rural Proofing in Living Labs

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Report summarising comparative analysis and lessons learned regarding implied functional geographies, the use of novel and place-based indicators in policy development processes and Rural Proofing in the LLs

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1. Introduction

Rural areas are diverse, and this diversity underpins their capacity to respond to pressing ecological, digital, and socio-economic transitions through local resources, functions and knowledge (RUSTIK D1.1, 2023). While this diversity is an important asset that can strengthen resilience and benefit rural communities, understanding and embedding it into policy and practice remains challenging.

Most existing policies rely on established metrics and indicator systems that often fail to capture the complexity and diversity of rurality and rural transition challenges. Evidence gaps arise not only because data are rarely collected at the scale where meaningful disparities, needs or capacities become visible, but also because policymaking continues to rely predominantly on traditional quantitative data (RUSTIK D4.1, 2023). Addressing these transition challenges therefore requires more holistic approaches that draw on a wider range of data sources and forms of knowledge, as well as tools that enable data to be used more effectively in policymaking.

Rural areas are increasingly recognised as active sites of experimentation. Living Labs (LLs) and similar experimental approaches can support transition processes through iterative learning and practice-based innovation, while supporting policy learning by producing policy-relevant data, evidence or capacities (Suitner, 2024; Kim et al., 2024). In this context, WP4 of the RUSTIK project explores how data-driven LL experiments in the 14 Pilot Regions, and their associated policy impact pathways, can make rural diversity, needs and capacities more visible and actionable in real policy settings. This approach is further extended through the piloting of a Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) model, which assesses how existing and emerging policies perform from a place-based rural perspective.

Earlier work within RUSTIK WP1 (RUSTIK D1.3, 2023) reviewed rural proofing approaches in England, Finland and the United States. This review led to the outline of a generic rural proofing framework at the local level, including a set of guiding questions and evidence-based analyses to assess the territorial impact of policies and strategies. Building on these insights, but following a different operational route, WP4 introduces and tests Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) as a complementary layer that brings elements of rural proofing closer to specific territories, policies and governance practices, rather than attempting to build a comprehensive local rural proofing system.

This Deliverable 4.3 aims to report on policy-relevant insights and lessons arising from the Living Lab process implemented across 14 Pilot Regions (see Figure 1), highlighting how the different stages interact to shape the generation and use of evidence for rural transition and policy adaptation. The Pilot Regions represent a diverse set of rural contexts and have chosen to address a range of transition challenges, including socio-demographic and economic issues (such as the needs of rural businesses and the development of sustainable food and forestry systems), environmental concerns (including natural resource management), and challenges related to digital connectivity and the digital divide.

Drawing on these diverse rural contexts, the Deliverable provides concrete empirical examples of how local experiments can inform policy learning and contribute to potential policy and

institutional adaptation. It also identifies the governance and data practices needed to make better use of rural evidence. In addition, it offers practical lessons on structuring robust data-driven experiments by using the Theory of Change (ToC) approach to link experimentation with policy action and transition outcomes, and the application of Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) as a complementary approach to “stress-test” strategies, programmes and legal reforms from a rural perspective. Together, these insights highlight ways for strengthening the responsiveness and fairness of rural policy across different territorial contexts.

Figure 1: Intersection between RUSTIK Living Lab cycles (circles) and WP4 Tasks (squares)

The report is structured into four main sections:

- First, it draws on RUSTIK Deliverable 4.2 (RUSTIK, D4.2, 2024) to present the key findings on the broader policy environment in the Pilot Regions, highlighting the main enablers and inhibitors within their governance and policy contexts. These factors shape how the Pilot Regions addressed their transition challenges and prepared for subsequent stages of the Living Lab experiments.
- Second, the report applies a Theory of Change approach to analyse intervention logics, strategies, and transition responses across the 14 Pilot Regions. This enables mapping of how transition responses connect to intermediate outcomes and policy impacts.
- Third, it draws on policy impact pathways, grounded in place-based literature, and provides empirical examples from the Living Labs. These illustrate how granular data can reveal the need for stronger cross-sectoral policy integration, more territorially tailored resource allocation, and more inclusive and cooperative multi-level governance, as well as how such insights can contribute to policy adaptation.

- Finally, the report presents findings from the Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) pilots conducted in five Pilot Regions, focusing on selected existing and proposed policies. It concludes by proposing a standardised model for DRP, designed to support scalable, context-sensitive implementation.

2. Overall approach and methodology

At the centre of the RUSTIK project is the recognition that rural areas are shaped by different transitions (socio-economic/demographic, environmental/climate and digital) and that they have different capacities to respond to these. To support the development of more effective and context-sensitive policies that can foster these transitions, RUSTIK project engaged 14 Pilot Regions to carry out targeted, data-driven Living Lab (LL) experiments designed to capture their specific challenges and opportunities (see Table 1).

Table 1: Overview of the RUSTIK Pilot Regions, transition challenges and Living Labs

Pilot Region	Transition challenge	Data needs	Living Lab geography
AT: Nockregion-Oberkärnten	Identifying needs of small rural businesses	Demographics, economic status, challenges faced by Small Rural Businesses, employment data	A group of 17 municipalities at LAU2 level covered by a regional development agency. Pop. 52,451.
BG: Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin	Strengthening the rural food systems	Local population access, farming cooperation, vocational schools, visitor habits	A group of 3 municipalities at LAU2 level covered by a LAG. Pop. 35,815.
DE: Rhein-Hunsrück	Making the region an attractive place to live and work for young people	Real-time data on people seeking jobs and apprenticeships, open positions. Qualitative surveying	NUTS3 region comprising 137 municipalities. Pop. 103,767
ES: Galicia	Reconciling land use and ownership	Land ownership, housing data, existing policy instruments	Non-contiguous group of 20 LAU2 municipalities. Pop. 40,652.
ES: Sant Miquel de Balenyà (Osona)	Improving quality of life via territorial and urban planning	Demographics, surveys, environmental, infrastructure data	1 municipality. Pop. 1,353.
FI: North Karelia	Integration of immigrants	Population trends, immigrant background, job numbers, integration statuses	NUTS3 region comprising 13 municipalities. Pop. 163,281.

IT: Garfagnana	Sustainable forestry for productive and environmental purposes + community projects	Social capital, quality of relationships, trust between people, reciprocity (qualitative)	A group of 35 municipalities at LAU2 level covered by a LAG. Pop. 87,585.
IT: Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara	Water availability and management for irrigation and production	Real-time data for water availability and demand	NUTS3 region comprising 127 municipalities. Pop. 1,071,974.
PL: Woj. Mazowieckie – Szydłowiecki powiat	Development of entrepreneurship through natural resources	Detailed employment structures, local resources analysis, entrepreneurial sector insights	A group of 5 municipalities at LAU2 level. Pop. 40,000.
PL: Woj. Świętokrzyskie	Reversing demographic decline through rural tourism development	Insights on spatial distribution, tourist dynamics, rural area conditions	NUTS2 region. Pop. 1,187,693.
SR: Zaječar	Development of tourism and short food supply chains	Data on local food system participants, consumer preferences, tourism relevance	NUTS3 region comprising 4 municipalities. Pop. 97,778.
SI: Osrednjeslovenska	Excess food management and food access in rural areas	Real-time excess food data, social exclusion stats, subjective wellbeing metrics	NUTS3 region comprising 25 municipalities. Pop. 555,293.
UK: Gloucestershire	Development of a resource and a strategy for enhanced digital inclusion	Assessing rural communities' digital access, skill set and confidence.	Group of 4 rural districts at LAU2 level. Pop. 397,824.
UK: Monmouthshire	Demographic change and youth retention	Reasons for youth migration, housing and educational/employment data, income limitations	Single county at NUTS3 level. Pop. 93,000.

Source: Adapted from RUSTIK Deliverable 1.2 and Deliverable 3.3

This report is structured around the four-step process followed by the Pilot Regions in planning and implementing their LL experiments. Each step builds on the previous one, forming a coherent narrative: from articulating the initial narrative of a desirable transition, through developing the intervention logic of their experiments (drawing on the Theory of Change approach), and finally assessing how data and evidence can generate policy impact and support the rural proofing of policies.

The remainder of this section details the methodology applied in each of these steps (see

Figure 2).

Figure 2: Four-step process for planning and implementing LL experiments

Step 1: Developing Transition Narratives

In the first step, Transition Narratives were developed for the Pilot Regions. These documents defined the scope of a locally grounded transition challenge to be addressed through the Living Lab (LL) experiments, while also mapping the relevant policy and institutional context. This work built on two earlier exercises, Institutional Mapping (July-August 2023) and Policy Panorama (September-October 2023), which identified key stakeholder interests, drivers for collaboration, as well as limitations and gaps within existing institutional and policy frameworks.

Each Transition Narrative also included a chapter on Transition Pathways, outlining initial plans for implementing the LL experiments through indicative sequences of events, policies, and actions expected to lead to meaningful outcomes. Taken together, the Transition Narratives provided a shared analytical baseline and a structured starting point for the subsequent design and refinement of the LL experiments.

Step 2: Co-creating Theory of Change models

In the second step, the Pilot Regions developed Theory of Change (ToC) model for their Living Lab (LL) experiments in co-creation with their partners. This exercise was integrated into the second LL cycle, which focused on experimentation with novel data. Its overall objective was to support the design of structured, policy-relevant data experiments by 1) surfacing and articulating key assumptions underpinning each intervention logic; 2) identifying risks and potential weak points; and 3) devising responses to strengthen the likelihood of successful implementation.

To guide this process, the WP4 team drafted guidelines centred on three basic elements of the ToC model: long-term outcomes, intermediate outcomes and policy actions, which the LL partners were tasked with developing. The process was conducted twice: at the beginning (April–June 2024) and at the end (October–December 2024) of the data experiment. The process was supported by bilateral discussions between the LL partners and the WP3 and WP4 teams, which helped structure and refine the ToC models. The results were then jointly reviewed and consolidated into structured models illustrating the intervention logic of the experiments. The final

output consisted of graphical illustrations and descriptions of 14 ToC models, presented in the second LL report (RUSTIK, D3.2, 2024).

The first step in reverse-engineering logic of the ToC approach of the LLs involved defining the long-term outcome of the data experiment. This outcome was directly linked to the transition challenge(s) selected by the LL. An important aspect of this was to establish the 'accountability ceiling', which functions as a critical boundary in the ToC process, separating the direct results of a data experiment from long-term impacts that remain outside the project's immediate control. Setting this ceiling was essential for managing (realistic) expectations, as it enabled partners to distinguish between the 'actionable knowledge' generated through the experiments and the wider regional transformations that depend on external institutional commitment.

Next, partners were asked to define intermediate outcomes, in other words tangible and measurable stepping stones leading towards the long-term objective. These intermediate outcomes could form multiple potential pathways, which may diverge or converge, but ultimately lead to the specified long-term objective. As part of the analysis, partners were asked to identify the key assumptions underpinning each intermediate outcome, along with the associated risks. This involved examining, for example, whether specific behavioural or operational expectations were placed on key actors, what the consequences might be if these expectations were not met, and the extent to which progress depended on external factors such as market conditions, shifts in public attitudes, or cultural dynamics. It also included assessing whether any cause-and-effect relationships required active community engagement or stakeholder buy-in. This structured analysis provided a more nuanced understanding of the conditions required for success and helped identify potential vulnerabilities and points of failure within the intervention logic.

Finally, partners were asked to specify the policy actions necessary to initiate and sustain the process. While there was initial ambiguity regarding the scope of this term, it was clarified that a policy action refers to a specific intervention or activity within the regional policy context designed to support the achievement of the experiment's long-term outcome. These actions serve as key links intervention logic chain, connecting the data experiment with broader regional impacts.

Importantly, these actions were treated as diagnostic interventions rather than mere administrative tasks. Their purpose was to identify existing gaps, whether in data, governance, or social needs, and to then validate assumptions regarding stakeholder interest and administrative capacity prior to full-scale policy implementation. This phase required partners to ensure that policy actions remained iterative, allowing for constant adjustment based on experimental feedback to maintain a robust and credible intervention logic.

Step 3: Identifying Pathways for Policy Impact

Towards the completion of the data experiments, partners reviewed the evidence generated through their experimental work to assess implications for selected policies. This represented a logical next step: while the ToC models capture ex ante assumptions about how change is expected to occur through the intervention logic, the policy impact pathways draw on obtained

evidence to examine what these findings imply in policy terms, namely how the evidence generated could inform policy learning and adaptation. This exercise was conducted between March-May 2025.

Three policy impact pathways were developed as an analytical framework to explore the different logics through which experimental evidence can inform policy direction and, over time, contribute to policy change. The identification of these pathways builds on the overarching objective of the experiments to support more evidence-based and place-sensitive policymaking. Drawing on the literature, which emphasises cross-sectoral integration, territorially sensitive resource allocation, and multi-level governance as core principles of place-based approaches (Barca, 2009, Pertoldi, Martina, et al (2022), Beer, 2023), these principles were used as a lens to interpret how experimental insights could inform policy.

The pathways were used by the LLs as an analytical framework to examine how these principles manifest in different experimental and governance contexts. This involved a process of contextualisation, building on the comparative analysis of institutional structures and policy contexts across the 14 Pilot Regions (RUSTIK D4.2, 2023), complemented by bilateral discussions with each LL team. Through this process, partners reflected on which pathway, or combination of pathways, was most relevant to their specific transition challenges, institutional settings, and emerging policy priorities.

Building on this, the LLs analysed how the evidence generated through their experiments, such as data on territorial disparities, cross-sectoral interdependencies, and governance dynamics, related to policy challenges and potential responses. The reflections collected from the LLs were subsequently analysed to identify recurring patterns and draw broader conclusions regarding policy learning and potential directions for change under each pathway.

This stage also informed subsequent steps of the work, including Cycle 3, and the selection of policies examined in the decentralised rural proofing (DRP) pilots.

Step 4: Pilot Testing a Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) model

Finally, between July 2025 and January 2026, a decentralised rural proofing (DRP) pilots were implemented in selected LLs, drawing on their experiments. Building on the conceptual DRP framework developed in WP4 Task 4.3(c), a common approach to DRP was agreed upon as the basis for small-scale pilots. The primary objective was to explore whether, and under what conditions, such a model can function effectively in different rural contexts. The DRP model emphasised bottom-up, place-based micro assessments, whereby local actors used existing data and contextual knowledge to reflect on how selected policies relate to rural needs, opportunities, and transition challenges. The participating Pilot Regions were chosen to represent diverse governance settings and to cover the three WP4 policy impact pathways.

To ensure a harmonised starting point across the five DRP pilots, in July 2025, the WP4 team issued a brief guidance note, *Decentralised Rural Proofing - Overall Approach* (see Annex 1). The

guidance clarified the objectives of the DRP pilots, the decentralised distribution of roles and responsibilities, and the link to the three WP4 policy impact pathways. It also defined a common five-step process, including: framing and guiding questions, data synthesis, micro-assessment, feedback and policy reflection, and reporting. Each Pilot Region subsequently adapted the common process to its specific policy focus, actor set-up and available evidence.

Figure 3: Five-step DRP process

Defining DRP scope, objectives and actors

In the first step, each selected Pilot Region specified the scope and objectives of its DRP pilot, identifying a specific policy focus closely linked to its transition challenge and pathway logic. The scope ranged from individual strategies to clusters of interlinked instruments, as well as national legal reforms examined from a rural and regional perspective. At the same time, each pilot identified a core group of actors, typically combining a coordinating ‘anchor institution’ (such as a university, LAG or regional council), and involving key policy owners and local stakeholders (e.g. municipalities, businesses, NGOs, and community organisations).

Framing guiding questions and preparing the evidence base

Partners then translated their transition challenges and policy focus into a concise set of guiding questions to structure the assessment, in line with the DRP guidance. Across the pilots, these questions consistently addressed themes such as accessibility and delivery of policy instruments, their coherence and alignment with local needs and existing initiatives, the adequacy of financial

and human resources, stakeholder participation and representation, and the differentiated impacts within rural areas. To support this analysis, each pilot case prepared a short evidence summary by synthesising relevant existing information. This included results from Institutional Mapping and the Policy Panorama, Transition Narratives, results from Cycle 2 data experiments, as well as local statistics and policy documents. Where critical information gaps were identified, some pilots complemented the analysis with targeted new data collection, for example through short surveys or ex post evaluation exercises.

Conducting micro assessments and feeding back findings

Using the guiding questions and evidence summaries, the pilots carried out micro-assessments of the selected policies or policy mixes. Rather than aiming for comprehensive impact evaluation, these assessments focused on how well the policies reflected the specific transition challenges, how they interacted with the existing institutional and policy environment, and where misalignments or missed opportunities could be observed. The methodological approach was adapted to local conditions and included combinations of desk analysis, structured or semi-structured interviews, questionnaires, focus groups and participatory workshops with relevant stakeholders. Preliminary DRP findings were then shared with relevant policy and governance actors at local, regional or national level through feedback meetings, workshops or reflection sessions. The outcomes were documented in short DRP reports describing the scope, methods, key findings and reflections on feasibility, transferability and the role of DRP as an enabling approach. These reports form the empirical basis for the cross-case comparative analysis of DRP presented in the analytical sections of this deliverable.

3. Analysis

3.1 Developing transition narratives

In the first step, Pilot Regions developed Transition Narratives (RUSTIK, D4.2, 2023), building on the earlier Institutional Mapping and Policy Panorama exercises. Together, these inputs provided an overview of stakeholder constellations and existing policy efforts related to the selected transitions (see Table 1). By examining the strengths, gaps and constraints of the institutional and policy environments in which the Living Lab (LL) experiments would be embedded, the Transition Narratives offered an initial framing of how these transitions could be explored and addressed through the LL experiments. This step marked the first structured reflection by the Pilot Regions on the potential role and contribution of their LL experiments, including the ways in which data generation and use could support transition processes. Deliverable 4.2 provided a detailed analysis of the Transition Narratives. The following section highlights the key findings from this deliverable that inform the subsequent steps in refining and implementing the LL experiments.

3.1.1 Institutional context and capacity for addressing transition

The capacity of regional and local rural communities to respond to transition challenges is strongly shaped by their institutional and governance contexts, which determine where responsibilities lie and how decisions, including funding allocations, are made. Across the RUSTIK Pilot Region countries, government arrangements vary substantially, reflecting a mix of unitary and federal systems with differing degrees of centralisation, decentralisation and autonomy (see Table 2).

In more centralised systems, policy priorities and instruments are largely defined at national level, leaving limited scope for regional and local authorities to tailor interventions to local needs. By contrast, decentralised systems tend to grant greater autonomy to sub-national actors, enabling more place-based policy responses. While a majority of the RUSTIK countries operate within decentralised systems, the extent of regional and local autonomy varies considerably. Three of the RUSTIK countries (Bulgaria, Slovenia and Serbia), have predominantly centralised governance structures.

Table 2: Overview of governance structures of the RUSTIK countries

Country	Described as centralised /decentralised in RUSTIK
AT	Decentralised with federal level, 9 Länder (states) and municipalities.
BG	Centralised with central and local governmental levels. In addition, there are deconcentrated regional state administrations at NUTS3 and six NUTS2 statistical regions without administrative power.
DE	Decentralised with federal level, 16 Länder (states), and local level (municipalities and districts).
ES	Decentralised with central level, varying levels of powers in 17 autonomous communities, provinces and municipalities.
FI	Decentralised with central, regional and local level.
IT	Decentralised with central level, regions (with varying autonomy), provinces and municipalities.
PL	Decentralised with central, (16) regional voivodeships, counties (powiats) and local communes.
SI	Centralised with central level and municipalities. In addition, there are 12 NUTS3 statistical regions without administrative power.
SR	Centralised with central level, provincial (one autonomous province), and local level. In addition, administrative districts.
UK	Decentralised with central level, devolved administrations in Scotland, Wales and N. Ireland, and local government.

Source: Authors own, partly adapted from Transition Narratives

Note: This table does not aim to provide a detailed analysis of governance arrangements. Instead, it indicates whether governance structures are broadly characterised as centralised or decentralised in RUSTIK deliverables, serving as a reference framework for subsequent analysis.

The overview of national arrangements in Table 2 provides a simplified overview of the country-level governance structures. While such arrangements can be interpreted and categorised in different ways depending on perspectives on governance, the table is intended to indicate where systems have been emphasised as leaning towards more centralised or decentralised forms of governance. However, this overview does not capture the diversity of institutional contexts across the RUSTIK Pilot Regions or their Living Labs, each of which operates within distinct constraints and opportunities for addressing transition challenges. Rather it serves as a reference framework for subsequent analysis, allowing specific institutional or policy issues to be interpreted in relation to the broader governance structures.

As noted earlier, the institutional mapping carried out by the Pilot Regions ahead of the Transition Narratives deliverable (RUSTIK D4.2, 2024) identified the profiles and competences of key institutions and actors in the Pilot Regions, along with an initial assessment of their relevance to the three broad transitions addressed by the RUSTIK project. This provided an initial overview of the profiles and competences of the actors and helped identifying which actors should be included in a more detailed analysis in the next stage of the LL experiments.

Drawing on the institutional mapping analysis, a consistent message emerges across the Pilot Regions: **addressing the transition challenges requires strong coordination and cooperation across governance levels, sectors and stakeholder groups**, underpinned by active participation, a shared understanding of and commitment to the transition challenges.

Two institutional factors were identified as particularly important in enabling such coordination and cooperation.

- First, **cooperative networks**, which are partnerships among stakeholders with shared interests and objectives, play a central role. Most Pilot Regions reported the presence of such networks, with Local Action Groups (LAGs) frequently cited as prominent examples (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). These networks were found to facilitate open dialogue and information exchange, build trust and mutual understanding, and enable the pooling of resources, expertise and influence in support of shared transition goals. In some cases, such networks also assume a broader coordinating role and can be considered institutional facilitators (see below).
- Second, **institutional facilitators**, typically organisations or formal structures that support coordination among the different actors and networks, were found to be critical in sustaining collaborative efforts. Nine Pilot Regions reported the presence of such facilitators, often including the Pilot Region partner itself (e.g. the Regional Association Nockregion in [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#) or the Regional Agency for Rural Development, Agader, in [Galicia](#)). These actors play a key role in coordinating cross-sectoral networks and bridging gaps between local, regional, national and EU levels of governance. A strong

central organisation with dedicated resources was also seen as crucial for maintaining continuity in multi-level collaboration (e.g. [Rhein-Hunsrück](#)).

Noted benefits of LAGs in fostering cooperation between stakeholders

- Extensive local experience and knowledge of community needs (e.g. [Garfagnana](#)), as such in a unique position to facilitate communication and cooperation between stakeholders.
- Bottom-up approach, enabling place-specific and context-sensitive solutions (e.g. [Osrednjeslovenska](#)).
- Broad representation of different sectors, stakeholders and perspectives (which promotes holistic understanding and alignment of interests) (e.g. [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#)).
- Power and interest in addressing the transition challenge (e.g. [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#)).

Source: *Transition Narratives*

Conversely, the absence of cooperative networks and institutional facilitators was found to significantly constrain transition capacity. In such contexts, collaboration tends to be fragmented, *ad hoc* and project-based, limiting continuity and undermining strategic alignment among actors. Without established cooperative networks, collaboration is often infrequent and short-term, making it difficult to address complex transition challenges in a sustained and coordinated way. Similarly, in the absence of an institutional facilitator, existing partnerships are more likely to remain isolated and localised, with weaker connections to wider regional dynamics and fewer opportunities for integration, scaling, and multi-level alignment. These challenges were evident, for example, in [Zaječar District](#), where cooperation was described as underdeveloped, fragmented and confined to specific sectors or local products.

While there was a relatively high level of shared understanding of the transition challenges in the Pilot Regions, several other cross-cutting barriers to effective cooperation were also identified, including power imbalances between bottom-up actors and top-down authorities (e.g. in [Gloucestershire](#), [Osona](#)), conflicting or competing interests among stakeholders (e.g. [Mazowieckie](#), [Świętokrzyskie](#)), limited involvement of key actors (e.g. lack of youth participation in [Rhein-Hunsrück](#)), and administrative barriers related to regulatory frameworks and resource constraints (e.g. [Zaječar District](#), [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#)).

In this context, several Pilot Regions highlighted the **potential of the RUSTIK Living Labs not only for data collection, but as shared spaces for coordination and engagement.** Living Labs were seen as offering a platform to connect actors and strengthen cooperation by fostering dialogue and joint action in areas where coordinated approaches could improve transition outcomes (e.g. [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#), [Gloucestershire](#), [Rhein-Hunsrück](#), [Mazowieckie](#)).

3.1.2 Policy context and capacity to address transition

Beyond institutional arrangements, the Transition Narratives examined the presence, and effectiveness of existing policies, and how well policy frameworks are equipped to respond to the selected transition challenges. A wide range of public policy measures were identified, including strategies, plans, laws/regulations, programmes, and other implementation instruments, that

directly or indirectly relate to the selected transition challenges. However, there is considerable variation in how clearly and consistently these challenges are embedded within existing policy frameworks.

The Transition Narratives highlighted differences in the governance levels at which policy alignment and coordinated action are pursued or achieved. In some Pilot Regions, transition objectives appear to be embedded within rather coherent multi-level governance arrangements (e.g. [Monmouthshire](#), [Garfagnana](#), [North Karelia](#)). In others, transition challenges were more strongly shaped by national-level policy frameworks (e.g. [Zaječar District](#)), which in some cases are subsequently translated into more concrete actions at regional or local level, reflecting a locally–nationally aligned approach (e.g. [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#)). The effectiveness of such alignment in addressing transition challenges varies. While there can be relatively formal alignment between local level solutions and national priorities, concerns have been raised for example about the potential prioritisation of national objectives over local needs. This can constrain the ability of local actors to fully utilise national frameworks (e.g. [Zaječar District](#), [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#)). Conversely, some other RUSTIK countries operate within more bottom-up, place-based policy approaches, where local or regional authorities play a central role in addressing the transition challenge in practice (e.g. [Mazowieckie](#)). Even in these cases, certain limitations remain, including possible dominance of specific actors whose interests may not always align with those at other governance levels. In addition, [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#) and [Rhein-Hunsrück](#) represent different governance contexts, as the federal level between the national and regional levels holds the primary policy competences relevant to addressing the identified transition challenges. It is notable that these examples provide a simplified picture, reflecting, at least in part, the diversity of institutional arrangements across the ten RUSTIK countries (see Table 2).

Nonetheless, the analysis indicates that **the effectiveness of policy measures in addressing transition challenges is shaped by the quality of coordination across governance levels (vertical) and among policy domains (horizontal).** While some Pilot Regions appear to demonstrate rather well-established multi-level governance arrangements that support strong coordination across levels of government and sectors (e.g. [Monmouthshire](#), [Garfagnana](#)), others are characterised by a stronger emphasis on vertical coordination, such as between local and higher levels of governance (e.g. [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#), [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#) and [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#)). In contrast, some regions place greater emphasis on horizontal cooperation, especially among local stakeholders (e.g. [Świętokrzyskie](#), [Mazowieckie](#), [Rhein-Hunsrück](#), [Gloucestershire](#), [North Karelia](#)). Several Pilot Regions also note examples of fragmented governance structures and insufficient vertical and horizontal coordination (due to various reasons including tensions at different levels, competition, or conflicts of interest between local actors), which in turn limit the coherence and effectiveness of policy action. Hence, the presence or absence of balanced coordination across levels and sectors has implications for policy coherence, stakeholder engagement, and the capacity to translate strategic objectives into effective and context-sensitive actions.

Examples of **mechanisms that have been established to support such dialogue and policy harmonisation across governance levels**, include national-level frameworks, locally driven initiatives (e.g. the LEADER programme and Local Action Groups), and monitoring and evaluation

systems. These mechanisms contribute to policy coherence by aligning objectives, coordinating implementation, and ensuring consistency across policy domains, while also enabling feedback loops between local, regional, national, and EU levels. The analysis nonetheless points to important trade-offs between policy harmonisation and local autonomy, with variation across Pilot Regions depending on governance structures and implementation capacity, as highly centralised approaches may constrain place-based innovation. This underscores the importance of balanced governance arrangements that combine top-down coordination with bottom-up engagement. In addition, funding mechanisms emerge as key factors for facilitating multi-level and cross-sectoral coordination, particularly where alignment with EU frameworks, funding cycles, and strategic priorities supports coherence across governance levels. The leveraging of EU, national, and regional funds has enabled several Pilot Regions to mobilise stakeholders, build institutional capacity, and align policy objectives, while also exposing challenges related to funding continuity, centralisation, and local autonomy.

Beyond the issues of policy coordination and harmonisation, the Transition Narratives also identified a number of other policy-related constraints, including.

Regulatory frameworks which can constrain local action where rules and strategic frameworks set at higher levels of government are overly rigid, complex or poorly aligned with local conditions. In some cases, gaps or ambiguities in legal frameworks further undermine the capacity of sub-national actors to respond effectively to transition challenges. Similar rigidity was also noted in **centrally defined funding conditions**.

Limitations related to economies of scale were also highlighted, particularly in remote rural areas and those facing demographic challenges. In such contexts, national or regional measures are often difficult to implement efficiently due to low population numbers or limited demand.

Several Pilot Regions reported a **gap between strategic priorities and implementation**, whereby high-level policy objectives are not sufficiently translated into concrete, actionable measures at local level. This weakens the practical relevance of strategies and reduces their impact on the ground. In addition, softer constraints, such as **limited confidence to act** at the local level and the **short-termism** planning horizons further hinder effective approaches.

Administrative and institutional capacity constraints were also frequently cited, including limited staff resources, gaps in expertise and leadership, and weaknesses in organisational coordination. These constraints affect both the effective use of existing policy instruments and the ability to design and implement new responses to transition challenges.

Taken together, these findings highlight that **the capacity of Pilot Regions to address transition challenges is shaped not only by the availability of relevant policy frameworks, but also by how these policies are coordinated, operationalised and supported by sufficient administrative and analytical capacity**.

3.1.3 Capacity of the overall policy environment to transition

Building on the analysis of institutional and policy contexts, Deliverable 4.2 provided an indicative assessment of how conducive the overall policy environment in the Pilot Regions was for

addressing the selected transition challenges. The assessment reflected the balance between enabling and constraining institutional and policy conditions, categorising Pilot Regions as having a *low*, *medium*, or *high* level of conduciveness. A low ranking indicated that institutional and policy constraints outweigh enabling factors, whereas medium and high rankings suggested that key facilitators are more prominent and constraints fewer or less severe. The main findings are summarised below.

1) Policy environment largely conducive to transition

Table 3: Moderate to high level of institutional and policy capacity

Conduciveness	Pilot Regions
Medium-High	Nockregion-Oberkärnten; North Karelia; Gloucestershire; Rhein-Hunsrück
High	Garfagnana; Parma-Piacenza-Ferrera; Monmouthshire

Source: Adapted from Deliverable 4.2, Institutional structures and policy panoramas in the Pilot Regions, 2024

Key institutional factors

Pilot Regions in this group were characterised by **relatively strong institutional capacity to collaborate and coordinate action**, reflected in high levels of stakeholder engagement and willingness to collaborate around the transition challenge. Cooperation was typically underpinned by:

- **A holistic, cross-sectoral approach,**
- **Cooperative networks** grounded in experience, broad stakeholder representation and bottom-up principles (e.g. LAGs and informal networks), and
- **The presence of institutional facilitators** with sufficient capacity and resources (often the Pilot Region partner) that actively coordinated these networks and actors and linked local, regional and national governance levels.

Across these Pilot Regions, collaboration was not only frequent but often also **strategic**, enabling coordinated responses rather than isolated initiatives.

A further key enabling factor was a **shared understanding of the transition challenge**. In most Pilot Regions, key actors recognised both the challenges and opportunities associated with the transition and acknowledged the need for collective action. This alignment of interests provided a strong foundation for cross-sectoral and multi-level cooperation.

Despite these strengths, the Pilot Regions also faced distinct inhibitors that constrained collaborative action.

- **Power imbalances** between bottom-up actors and top-down authorities,
- **Resource limitations** affecting the scope or continuity of collective action, and
- **Mistrust or limited interest** among specific stakeholder groups.

Moreover, **engagement gaps** persisted, particularly among groups most affected by the transition but insufficiently integrated into planning and decision-making processes, such as young people (e.g. [Monmouthshire](#), [Rhein-Hunsrück](#)) or small businesses (e.g. [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#)).

Key policy factors

From a policy perspective, this group benefited from **relatively coherent and comprehensive policy approach** that aligned objectives and actions across governance levels. This was supported by different mechanisms such as policy harmonisation frameworks, inter-agency cooperation, and fund coordination. Clear roles, balanced power relations, and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms further strengthened policy coherence and effective implementation.

Targeted, place-sensitive strategies were a particular strength. Policy measures addressing transition challenges in the Pilot Regions, such as strategies, plans, programmes, and other implementation instruments, vary widely in their binding nature, territorial scale (national, regional, or local), focus (explicit or implicit), ambition, and assessed impact. Notably, coordinated strategic and policy frameworks in which overarching national or higher-level objectives are translated into more targeted sub-national actions are particularly well suited to addressing the multi-faceted nature of transition challenges. By enabling integration and coordination across multiple thematic areas and levels of governance, such frameworks support more coherent and effective policy responses.

Funding also plays a critical enabling role, not only by supporting concrete actions but by enabling coordination itself, for example through dedicated resources for multi-level and cross-sectoral policy and stakeholder coordination.

Even in this group, the potential of policy measures was not always fully realised. In several Pilot Regions, strategic priorities are not consistently translated into effective local action, often due to limited availability or use of granular data needed to tailor interventions (e.g. [Rhein-Hunsrück](#), [North Karelia](#), [Parma and Piacenza](#)). In a smaller number of cases, regulatory constraints were also noted to act as barriers, such as rigid forest management frameworks in [Garfagnana](#).

2) Policy environment not conducive to transition

Table 4: Limited level of institutional and policy capacity

Conduciveness	Pilot Regions
Low	Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin; Mazowieckie; Świętokrzyskie; Zajecar District
Low / Medium	Galicia; Sant Miquel de Balenyà; Osrednjeslovenska

Source: Adapted from Deliverable 4.2

Key institutional factors

In this group, **constraining factors were assessed to be both more numerous and more severe.** A core issue was the limited capacity for coordination, often linked to the absence of structured

cooperation mechanisms. As a result, collaboration tended to rely on infrequent or ad hoc interactions rather than sustained collaboration.

That said, this group also contained important positive exceptions, such as functioning cooperation networks in [Woj. Świętokrzyskie](#), the bottom-up coordination role of LAGs in [Osrednjeslovenska](#), and the network of actors established by the Pilot Region partner (AGADER) in [Galicia](#). These examples suggest a good basis for strengthening actions.

The quality of cooperation was uneven and often affected by diverging interests, difficulties in building consensus on transition priorities, demographic factors (e.g. generational gaps), and administrative or regulatory constraints. Limited resources and local capacity further undermined coordinated responses to the transition challenges

Engagement gaps were also noted, with key stakeholders (e.g. entrepreneurs or strategically relevant institutions) sometimes insufficiently involved, unwilling to engage, or lacking influence, thereby constraining coordinated responses.

Key policy factors

From a policy perspective, many Pilot Regions in this group operated within fragmented policy environments, marked by unclear divisions of responsibility, limited dialogue across policy silos, and weak coordination between governance levels. This fragmentation can undermine strategic coherence and hinder integrated approaches to the transition challenge

Some Pilot Regions in this group are additionally characterised by a predominantly top-down policy approach, where national-level frameworks shape local action (e.g. [Zaječar District](#), [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#)). While local agendas are often aligned with national priorities, this alignment may favour national objectives over place-specific needs and limit local ownership.

Resource constraints further exacerbated these challenges. While some Pilot Regions succeed in leveraging available funding, many faced issues related to the short-term nature of funding, limited continuity across policy cycles, and the absence of dedicated resources targeting the transition challenge.

Finally, the absence of targeted, place-based policy or strategic frameworks was a major constraint in several Pilot Regions. Local initiatives, often voluntary and informal, such as local food festivals in [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), play a valuable role but tend to be fragmented, short-term and weakly connected to broader development strategies, leaving significant potential underutilised.

3.1.4 Preparing for Living Lab implementation

As part of the Transition Narratives, Pilot Regions outlined initial Transition Pathways that intended to capture their emerging plans for implementing the Living Lab (LL) experiments. These pathways served as a forward-looking element, structuring early thinking around the sequence of events, policies, and actions needed to address the identified transition challenges, and helping to set the direction for the subsequent stages of the LL experiments. At this stage, Pilot Regions

were at different points in their planning processes, resulting in varying levels of detail across the Transition Pathways. While some pathways were already relatively well developed, others remained indicative and open to further refinement, reflecting the iterative nature of transition planning. Nevertheless, the Transition Pathways provided an important opportunity for early reflection and a foundation for subsequent support to Pilot Regions, informing the drafting of Theory of Change models that guide the planning and implementation of the later stages of their LL experiments.

3.1.5 Key takeaways

The following summarises key takeaways for the Living Lab planning and next steps.

Key takeaways

- **A contextual overview.** The Transition Narratives set out a structured overview of transition challenges, institutional and policy contexts and stakeholder constellations, providing a shared reference point to align perspectives and inform Living Lab design.
- **Enablers and bottlenecks for collaboration.** The analysis highlighted the importance of cooperative networks and institutional facilitators in enabling coordination, while also revealing common barriers such as fragmented cooperation, power imbalances, limited participation and resource constraints.
- **Diversity in policy environments.** By assessing the overall policy environment (institutional and policy landscapes), the exercise distinguished between contexts ranging from multi-level policy frameworks that support coordinated action to more fragmented or top-down systems that can constrain place-based responses.
- **Scope for influence.** By examining the institutional and policy landscapes, the exercise helped identify constraints and opportunities that can influence each Living Lab's scope for action, supporting a more context-sensitive experiment design.
- **Foundation for a Theory of Change development.** Early thinking on sequences of actions and expected outcomes of the Living Lab experiments created a foundation for further methodological development, particularly the drafting of Theory of Change models in the next stage of the Living Lab implementation.

3.2 Theory of Change

The preceding section presented empirical findings from the first step of the process, which focused on understanding the policy and institutional context in which the Living Lab (LL) experiments were embedded. This step enabled LLs to identify relevant policies, stakeholders

and governance dynamics related to their selected transition challenges, as well as key opportunities and challenges, particularly in terms of decision-making mechanisms and cooperation structures that may support or constrain place- and evidence-based policy approaches.

Building on this, LLs developed Theory of Change (ToC) models as a second step of the process to structure their experiments. The initial transition framings, gaps, and challenges identified through the Transition Narratives were iteratively refined and translated into structured intervention logics. These guided decisions on the focus of the experimentation, the types of data to be generated, and the intended policy relevance of the results.

This section analyses the resulting ToC models across the 14 Pilot Regions. It examines how the LLs structured their data experiments through ToC models and corresponding intervention logics, and how these models' conceptualised pathways from experimentation to broader rural transitions. In this sense, the ToC models translated the broader institutional and policy conditions identified in the Transition Narratives into more explicit intervention logics, specifying how LL experiments were expected to contribute to change under context-specific assumptions and constraints.

The analysis draws primarily on the second LL reports (RUSTIK D3.2, 2024), which contained graphical illustrations and descriptions of the ToC models, as well as on bilateral meetings with the 14 Pilot Regions during which the models were refined and stress tested. In line with the methodological approach, particular attention was paid to long-term outcomes, intermediate outcomes, policy actions, and the assumptions and risks underpinning each intervention logic.

The section is organised into six sub-sections. It begins by examining cross-cutting assumptions and risks identified across the ToC approaches. The remaining sections are structured around five broad thematic groupings, building on the initial clustering in D3.2 and further refined to reflect the transition pathways pursued by the LLs.

Each thematic group brings together LLs that:

- Address broadly similar transition challenges and long-term objectives (e.g. demographic/retention challenges vs. resource governance vs. evidence and planning capacity); and
- Rely on distinct but internally consistent intervention rationales, meaning that the expected change mechanism differs across groups.

These five groupings will also be used in D5.1 (RUSTIK D5.1, forthcoming) to enable a consistent comparison across LLs. The thematic groups discussed here are: Demographic Retention and Social Inclusion, Sustainable Food and Forestry Systems, Strengthen Rural Businesses and Land Use and Natural Resources and Data Tools for future planning. While each group shares broadly similar long-term ambitions, they differ in the resources mobilised and the intervention logics through which change is expected to occur. Table 5 provides an overview of the five thematic groupings used to structure the analysis of the Living Lab Theory of Change models.

Table 5: Overview of the five thematic groups

Thematic Groups	Living Labs	Description
Demographic retention and Social Inclusion	Monmouthshire; North Karelia; Rhein-Hunsrück; Osrednjeslovenska	Focuses on improving the inclusion of groups whose needs are insufficiently reflected in existing policies, such as young people, immigrants and people at risk of poverty, with wider benefits for well-being, demographic balance and local development.
Sustainable food and forestry systems	Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin; Zaječar District; Garfagnana	Focuses on better connecting primary production with local and regional consumption, processing, tourism and short value chains, while making better use of local natural resources and products.
Strengthening rural businesses	Mazowieckie; Świętokrzyskie; Nockregion-Oberkärnten	Focuses on improving knowledge, visibility and support for rural businesses, including tourism-related enterprises and businesses linked to local natural assets, to strengthen regional attractiveness and economic resilience.
Land Use and Natural Resource Management	Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara; Galicia	Focuses on improving the governance of key natural resources, particularly water and land, in response to pressures such as drought, wildfire risk, land abandonment, land fragmentation and competing resource demands.
Data tools for future planning	Sant Miquel de Balenyà (Osona) ; Gloucestershire	Focuses on developing granular data tools, such as a quality-of-life index or data analysis dashboard, to reveal local disparities and support evidence-based planning, service provision and policy decisions.

Source: Adapted from the Living Lab transition choice summaries and the grouping applied in WP5

3.2.1 Cross-cutting assumptions and risks

As outlined in Section 2, a key objective of the ToC exercise is to surface and articulate the assumptions underpinning the intervention logic, as well as to identify risks and weak points. While the ToC models capture specific assumptions and risk regarding each ToC element (long-term outcomes, intermediate outcomes and policy actions), several common patterns emerge across all LLs. These include a set of foundational assumptions and recurring risks that reflect the shared challenges of applying ToC approaches within complex rural governance systems. In particular, they highlight issues related to varying administrative capacity, the level of policy coordination, the extent and quality of stakeholder engagement, and the degree of local room for manoeuvre.

The most prevalent assumption across the Pilot Regions was that place-based insights and fine-grained, spatialised data would enhance policy effectiveness. There was a shared belief that addressing information shortages or mismatches could influence stakeholder behaviour, for example in migration decisions, business cooperation, or natural resource management. Closely

linked to this was the assumption of institutional receptivity, whereby regional actors and public administrations were expected to be both willing and capable of integrating new data-driven findings into existing workflows and decision-making processes. In addition, many ToC models also implicitly relied on grassroots capacity, assuming that locally driven initiatives could complement or compensate for limitations in formal institutional structures.

Alongside these assumptions, several cross-cutting risks were identified. A key risk was that the main drivers of regional change, such as national labour laws, global market trends, or macro-economic shifts, lay entirely beyond the direct influence of local policy experiments, such as RUSTIK. As a result, local efforts remained vulnerable to external factors they could not control. Internally, political volatility and shifting priorities presented significant risks, as the long-term nature of territorial transitions was often at odds with short-term political cycles, and elections can frequently decouple long-term goals from active policy support.

Another recurring risk concerned the limited preparedness for engagement. This could manifest as a mismatch between the technical complexity of new tools and the digital, logistical or cultural capacity of stakeholders to adopt them. Finally, implementation was frequently jeopardised by resource constraints, including limited financial and human resources, as well as the risk of institutional internalisation, whereby the rural voice could become less visible when strategies were absorbed into administrative processes without sustained public engagement.

Figure 4: Cross-cutting Assumptions and Risks

3.2.2 Theory of Change approaches

Demographic retention and Social Inclusion

(Pilot Regions: *Monmouthshire, North Karelia, Rhein-Hunsrück, Osrednjeslovenska*)

In the first thematic group, Pilot Regions applied the ToC approach to address socio-economic transition challenges linked to demographic decline and social inclusion. While the primary focus of the long-term outcomes was to ensure that their territories remained attractive and inclusive,

they pursued this shared goal through different resources and intervention logics. For [Monmouthshire](#) and [Rhein-Hunsrück](#), the overarching long-term outcome was to achieve demographic balance by strengthening local employment and training opportunities, making their regions attractive places especially for young people to live and work, thereby addressing labour deficits and apprenticeship vacancies. [North Karelia](#) shared this vision but focused more specifically on social integration measures to retain its immigrant population, slowing demographic decline and addressing workforce gaps in critical sectors such as healthcare. [Osrednjeslovenska](#) linked demographic concerns to social cohesion by emphasising resource redistribution and environmental sustainability measures to reduce social exclusion and the regional environmental footprint.

To bridge the gap toward these long-term outcomes, the identified intermediate outcomes centred on strengthening local knowledge base and reinforcing institutional networks. [Rhein-Hunsrück](#) and [North-Karelia](#) both prioritised creating stronger links between regional employers and potential employees, whether they were local school graduates or immigrants, in order to lower barriers for hiring and integration. In [Monmouthshire](#), the intermediate outcome centred on ensuring that data generated through the LL experiment directly informed specific local strategies, ensuring policy makers to better understand and respond to the needs of local communities. Similarly, [Osrednjeslovenska](#) emphasised the development of synthesised and structured knowledge on available resources and community needs to support more informed decision-making. These intermediate outcomes relied on the assumption that regional actors were willing and able to integrate new findings into their existing practices. A key risk at this level was the limited preparedness of stakeholders to engage, as well as the absence of appropriate intermediaries with the capacity to implement the proposed measures. In [Osrednjeslovenska](#), this related specifically to the need for Local Action Groups (LAGs) or community hubs to possess the logistical knowledge and organisational capacity required for managing complex systems such as food redistribution. In [Rhein-Hunsrück](#), similar challenges arose in the form of communication gaps, where regional SMEs may have been unequipped to reach the youth through the digital channels they use.

The policy actions designed by these Pilot Regions to trigger change focus on three main areas: developing data-driven decision-making support tools, raising awareness within public administrations, and activating grassroots capacities to foster regional vitality. Several of these interventions have a strong analytical dimension, as they seek to embed localised evidence into formal administrative strategies and strategic planning frameworks. For example, [Monmouthshire](#) utilises data dashboards to support targeted, place-based decision-making, while [Rhein-Hunsrück](#) incorporates findings from its data experiments into strategic frameworks such as the District Development Concept (KEK) and LEADER projects. In [North-Karelia](#), policy actions are directed toward utilising wellbeing questionnaires and interviews with local companies to foster a dialogue that helps municipalities recognise the workforce potential of foreigners. Complementing these evidence-driven approaches, some regions also address social gaps through bottom-up community services, such as [Osrednjeslovenska's](#) use of transferable templates to facilitate the redistribution of excess resources to vulnerable groups.

These policy actions rely on the fundamental assumption that place-based insights can enhance the effectiveness of existing policies, and that regional actors are willing and able to integrate new

knowledge into their practices. However, the regions face significant implementation risks. These include constraints such as limited funding for community measures in [Osrednjeslovenska](#) and challenges in securing sufficient participation rates in surveys in [Monmouthshire](#) to ensure statistically significant results. Additionally, broader governance risks, such as tightening public finances and shifting political agendas, are perceived as potential barriers that could lead to municipal decision-makers to ignore identified issues.

Figure 5: Demographic retention & Social Cohesion synthesis

Sustainable Food and Forestry Systems

(Pilot Regions: [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), [Zaječar District](#), [Garfagnana](#))

Sustainable Food and Forestry Systems group applies the ToC approach to address socio-economic transitions by leveraging local natural resources. Across these Pilot Regions, the shared narrative centres on transforming raw local produce, whether food or timber, into higher-value territorial assets that can drive economic restructuring and community regeneration. The envisioned long-term outcomes are rooted in the assumption that local natural resource systems possess untapped potential to drive territorial growth and resilience. However, this potential is activated through different resource bases and distinct intervention logics. In [Garfagnana](#), the focus is on developing multifunctional forest-use models that increase the value added of timber while integrating sustainable resource management with community regeneration projects aimed at creating new job opportunities and attracting new residents. Similarly, [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) aims to transform local food into a distinctive territorial brand that captures additional value,

relying on market differentiation and formalised business cooperation as key levers. A specific long-term outcome for [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) is to decrease the significant share of the shadow economy in the food sector by encouraging legal cooperation and registered business practices. Importantly, the [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) LL identifies that such informal practices are frequently driven by efforts to provide high-quality, fresh, and seasonal food in a context where existing regulations often act as a barrier to formalisation. The [Zaječar District](#) pursues a broader form of economic restructuring by shifting towards labour-intensive services and higher value-added activities within the short food supply chain, thereby repositioning the local economy within more competitive market segments.

To bridge the gap toward these long-term goals, the intermediate outcomes focus on increasing awareness, strengthening partnerships, and fostering cross-sectoral synergies between food systems and the hospitality/tourism sector. For instance, [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), efforts centre on mapping local food systems to identify gaps in the current agricultural and regulatory frameworks that hinder local food development. At the same time, this process raises awareness to paves the way for a new, dedicated local food policy, which currently does not exist. In the [Zaječar District](#), the intermediate outcome centres on summarising findings to support evidence-based policymaking and identifying key stakeholders in the hospitality industry to build connections between local producers and tourism-related businesses. [Garfagnana](#) emphasises fostering new partnerships and reaching out to the most vulnerable populations in remote areas to ensure access to policy calls is inclusive. The assumption is that stakeholders will show enough enthusiasm to adopt new operating models. However, risks include deep-seated cultural barriers, such as a widespread stereotype that cooperation is culturally “unnatural”, and significant human or financial capacity limitations among local stakeholders to turn data results into actionable steps.

The policy actions designed to trigger these changes focused on formalising new governance tools, fostering collaborative frameworks, and addressing specific infrastructural bottlenecks necessary for territorial food and forestry systems. Several of these interventions had a pronounced governance nature, as they sought to embed local resources into formal administrative agendas and strategic funding streams. In several cases, this involved leveraging or adapting existing policy instruments. For example, [Garfagnana](#) was designing intervention remits for upcoming LEADER calls and promoting public-private partnerships through a ‘local project approach’, while [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) was working to formally include food on the local policy agenda for the first time. In the [Zaječar District](#), policy actions focused on facilitating multi-level stakeholder dialogue to overcome market obstacles, extending discussions to the national level when local jurisdiction was exceeded. Alongside these governance-oriented measures, the regions also addressed practical value-chain constraints that hinder formalisation and market access. This included investments in missing processing infrastructure, such as [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin’s](#) support for laboratory examinations for beekeepers to enable registered direct sales. Across cases, these policy actions rested on the assumption of sufficient municipal autonomy, whereby the local administrations had the authority to implement such measures. At the same time, they faced systemic risks that cut across contexts, including corruption, state capture, political instability, and rigid regulatory frameworks. For example, in [Garfagnana](#), forest management rules, particularly the current carbon credit regulations, were perceived as

insufficient to generate new opportunities. More broadly, these were often perceived as structural barriers that were difficult to address in the short term.

Figure 6: Sustainable Food and Forestry Systems synthesis

Strengthening Rural Businesses

(Pilot Regions: *Mazowieckie*, *Świętokrzyskie*, *Nockregion-Oberkärnten*)

The Pilot Regions within this group focused on strengthening rural businesses by moving from data-driven insights toward systemic economic transitions that enhance regional resilience. A central objective was to tackle unfavourable demographic processes, specifically ageing and the outmigration of young people and women, by boosting the visibility of, and knowledge about, local enterprises. Across *Mazowieckie*, *Świętokrzyskie*, and the *Nockregion-Oberkärnten*, long-term outcomes focused on fostering socio-economic transitions that enhance regional attractiveness and economic resilience through the strategic use of local assets. However, these regions operationalised this ambition through different resources and intervention logics. Broadly, these regions pursued this ambition by combining economic diversification, tourism-based development, and the institutionalisation of support for small rural businesses. In *Mazowieckie*, this outcome was envisioned as economic restructuring toward higher value-added activities and labour-intensive services, leveraging the area’s natural resources and cultural heritage to diversify the regional economy. Similarly, *Świętokrzyskie* aimed to stimulate attractive agrotourism development to create new jobs and specifically stop the outmigration of young people, using farm-based tourism and local value chains as key drivers. *Nockregion-Oberkärnten* sought to

establish the region as an attractive place to live and work by identifying the specific needs of small rural businesses (SRBs) and ensuring they were supported by permanent networks, thereby institutionalising business support structures. A shared underlying assumption was that strengthening local identity and social capital could contribute to reversing negative demographic and economic trends in regions experiencing functional decline. However, achieving these long-term outcomes was not without risk, as shifts in political priorities and deep-seated institutional or legal barriers could hinder the implementation of sustained structural change.

To bridge the gap between the LL experiments and long-term outcomes, partners identified critical intermediate outcomes. Across the three regions, these focused on generating usable evidence, identifying concrete support needs, and building a stronger basis for strategic action and future funding. In [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#), this involved strengthening the role of small businesses in regional decision-making and clearly defining the actions required to support them. [Świętokrzyskie](#) focused on providing data-backed recommendations for its 2025 tourism development strategy and identifying 'model' agrotourism farms that served as benchmarks for best practice. In [Mazowieckie](#), efforts centred on summarising data findings to support evidence-based policymaking and scaling analytical models to other municipalities in the region. The achievement of these intermediate outcomes rested on the assumption that fine-grained, spatially disaggregated data would capture the interest of stakeholders and provide a compelling base for future funding. However, a common risk identified across the cases was low stakeholder engagement. For example, [Świętokrzyskie](#) noted the limited willingness of farm owners to actively participate in research or adopt model solutions, while [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#) acknowledged that excluding even a few municipalities from data mapping could undermine the creation of a comprehensive regional picture.

The policy actions designed to trigger these outcomes focused heavily on targeted stakeholder engagement, capacity building, and the creation of regional brands and infrastructure. Overall, these actions combined awareness-raising and dialogue-oriented measures with more practical efforts to develop tourism assets, support local products, and strengthen cooperation networks. These actions included efforts to shift institutional priorities, such as [Nockregion-Oberkärnten's](#) stakeholder meetings with mayors to highlight the relevance of small enterprises compared to large-scale industry. Other approaches involved developing specialised tourism infrastructure and new rural products, alongside the strengthening of cooperation networks among local producers, as demonstrated in [Świętokrzyskie](#). Furthermore, regions facilitated multi-level dialogue to identify and address systemic obstacles, with [Mazowieckie](#) expanding discussions between entrepreneurs, residents, and authorities from the local level to the national stage. A key underlying assumption was that constant dialogue would enable local authorities to serve as effective intermediaries capable of maintaining long-term interest among entrepreneurs. However, several risks persisted. Notably, misaligned interests and timelines could emerge, as the short-term profit expectations of business owners could conflict with the slow-moving nature of place-branding and identity-building exercises. Additionally, regions needed to navigate the risk of governance de-prioritisation, whereby local administrations could continue to assign limited importance to sectors such as tourism when making strategic and funding decisions.

Figure 7: Strengthen Rural Businesses synthesis

Land Use and Natural Resource Management

(Pilot Regions: [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#), [Galicia](#))

In the thematic group focused on land use and natural resource management, partners applied the ToC approach to bridge the gap between fragmented resource governance and long-term environmental resilience. The long-term outcomes envisioned across these pilot regions centred on achieving systemic socio-economic and environmental transitions through the more strategic use of key resources such as land and water. Although the regions were affected by different territorial challenges, they converged around improving the governance and strategic use of key natural resources in ways that would strengthen both environmental resilience and local development. In [Galicia](#), this was articulated through the reconciliation of land use and land ownership, a goal intended to drastically reduce abandoned land, thereby mitigating wildfire risks and stimulating local economic activity. Similarly, the [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#) region aimed for the long-term improvement of water availability and efficiency for agriculture and the food industry, while simultaneously building stable institutional networks for innovation and information exchange. These long-term goals rested on the assumption that regional administrative priorities would remain stable over time. However, important risks persisted. In [Galicia](#), shifting political landscapes or post-election administrative restructuring could reduce the priority given to these specific policy measures. In [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#), the main risk lay in overcoming deep-seated data fragmentation across diverse stakeholders, which could hinder a fully integrated governance system.

To move toward these long-term outcomes, the regions identified intermediate outcomes that focused on demonstrating the viability of pilot approaches, improving the evidence base for decision-making, and creating clearer foundations for future scaling and resource allocation. For the [Galician](#) partners, the focus was on successfully expanding the number of ‘model settlements’ and reinforcing existing pilots to prove the initiative’s scalability and impact to local communities. In the [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#) pilot, intermediate progress was measured by the production of vulnerability maps and the identification of geo-localised investment needs, which were intended to provide a framework for more efficient resource allocation. A critical assumption for these milestones was that increased transparency regarding resource vulnerabilities would foster a more collaborative institutional environment. Yet, there was a risk that the public authorities could lack the administrative or budgetary capacity to handle a surge in demand if these pilot initiatives proved too successful. For example, in [Galicia](#), there was a concern regarding the potential for dozens or even hundreds of new applications for settlements. Additionally, in [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#), there was a risk that stakeholders could prioritise immediate, concrete short-term results over the more complex and gradual ‘intellectual construction’ required to link these intermediate milestones with long-term strategic transitions.

The policy actions designed to catalyse these changes relied heavily on the development of novel, evidence-based tools and intensive stakeholder participation. Overall, these actions combined technical decision-support instruments with qualitative inquiry and institutional coordination to improve governance of land and water resources. In [Galicia](#), this approach centred on the development of a spatial decision-support system to rank and prioritise applications for new model settlements, based on a combination of biophysical and socio-economic indicators. This was intended to ensure that resources would be concentrated where they could generate the greatest impact. This technical action was complemented by qualitative research, including interviews with land technicians and owners, to understand evolving motivations and intergenerational attitudes towards land management. Similarly, in the [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#) pilot region, efforts focused on compiling comprehensive inventories of existing data and conducting surveys among collective consortia. These activities supported the design of localised interventions and revision of regional water management instruments. These policy actions were underpinned by the assumption that bridging information gaps between institutions would strengthen their collective capacity to implement climate adaptation strategies. However, a key risk lay in the potential misalignment between the tools developed and the practical motivations of landowners or the operational realities of local authorities. This underscored the need for ongoing monitoring and adjustment to ensure that the prioritisation mechanisms and intervention designs would remain realistic and effective.

Figure 8: Land Use, Natural Resource Management synthesis

Data tools for future planning

(Pilot Regions: *Sant Miquel de Balenyà (Osona)*, *Gloucestershire*)

In the thematic group focused on data tools for future planning, the application of the ToC approach supported a shift towards evidence-based governance through the development of localised metrics that inform long-term resilience and equity. The primary long-term outcomes pursued by these regions centred on enhancing community well-being and institutional capacity through data-driven decision-making. Although these ambitions were grounded in different local contexts, the illustrated cases below used localised evidence to improve how needs were understood and addressed over time. In *Sant Miquel de Balenyà*, the ultimate goal was to enhance overall quality of life, while in *Gloucestershire*, the focus was on empowering the voluntary, community, and social enterprise (VCSE) sector to become more data-driven and confident in responding to client needs. These long-term ambitions rested on the assumption that place-based evidence and community-led data were essential prerequisites for achieving socio-economic resilience and digital equity. However, achieving these outcomes was subject to significant risks. In particular, shifting political priorities or the ‘internalisation’ of strategies by higher-level governing bodies could bypass the community-level insights that the ToC approach was intended to elevate.

To bridge the gap toward these long-term outcomes, partners identified intermediate outcomes that prioritised the prototyping and refinement of specific analytical tools. Beyond tool creation,

these intermediate steps also aimed to improve data consistency, reveal unmet information needs, and build stakeholder confidence in the use of new methods. Key initiatives included the development of a Quality of Life (QoL) index in [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#) to assess disparities between neighbourhoods, and a SMART dashboard in [Gloucestershire](#) designed to help service providers assess their impact. A critical intermediate step involved standardising data collection and identifying existing data gaps through stakeholder engagement. Examples included the participatory workshops held in [Gloucestershire](#) or the use of citizen participation tools like Maptionnaire in [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#). These milestones rested on the assumption that local stakeholders and citizens would be willing and able to engage in data generation and that sufficient trust existed to embrace new digital practices. A key risk at this stage was institutional or stakeholder ambivalence. For example, funding for rural digital support was dispersed among district-level organisations with deep local knowledge. Bringing this into a single network (such as the PRP's DAISI¹) required cross-organisational trust, co-operation and reformed funding arrangements.

Finally, the policy actions identified to realise these outcomes involved integrating these new data tools directly into strategic planning and advocacy processes. In practice, this meant linking locally generated evidence to planning, representation, and resource allocation processes at different governance levels. In [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#), the QoL index was designed to inform targeted interventions and ensure that local policy processes were grounded in neighbourhood-level realities. Similarly, in [Gloucestershire](#), partners leveraged their SMART dashboard to inform national and local efforts on 'minimum digital living standards' and to expand the reach of the network to ensure that the rural stakeholders in the county had a voice and that rural was not omitted in the discussions on digital equity and tackling the digital divide. These actions rested on the assumption that regional and national policy environments would remain receptive to localised data and that sufficient funding would be available for implementation. However, their effectiveness was subject to external risks beyond the partners' direct control. These included local government reforms expected in 2027 or the emergence of new national policy arrangements that could override local digital or social strategies. Throughout this process, the ToC approach provided a framework to the regions to continuously refine their strategies and to respond to a changing environment while keeping their data-driven objectives at the forefront of their transition responses.

¹ Digital Accessibility, Inclusion, Support and Innovation.

Figure 9: Data tools for future planning synthesis

3.2.3 Key takeaways

This subsection synthesises the cross-case patterns emerging from the Theory of Change (ToC) models developed across the 14 Pilot Regions. It distils the shared intervention logic, specifically what the Living Labs expected data-driven experiments to trigger and identifies the main implications of this logic for feasibility, uptake, and pathways towards policy learning. In doing so, it provides the bridge to the next step of the analysis, which asks how experiment-generated evidence is translated into tangible policy impact pathways.

The following summarises key takeaways for the Theory of Change and next steps.

- **Shared intervention logic (despite thematic diversity)**
 - Across the 14 Pilot Regions, the ToC models converged around a common mechanism: **data-driven Living Lab experimentation was expected to produce actionable learning** that could inform rural policy adaptation. While the long-term ambitions differed (demographic retention, business resilience, natural resource governance, future planning), the expected translation chain was broadly similar.

- **From evidence to policy required a translation process**
Data experiments were framed as **means rather than** outcomes. Impact was expected to merge through the development of **intermediate capacities**, such as enhanced coordination, improved use of evidence, networks, awareness, and policy-oriented interpretation rather than through data generation alone.
- **Assumptions and risks mattered as feasibility conditions, not as checklists**
The cross-case synthesis indicated that the assumptions/risks identified earlier functioned as critical opportunities/constraints on evidence uptake, rather than as static list of factors. Specifically, they revealed a specific mindset that influences:
 - whether institutions could absorb findings into workflows;
 - whether stakeholders could and would engage;
 - whether intermediaries existed to translate evidence into policy language;
 - whether external drivers and governance priorities remained sufficiently stable to sustain learning over time.
- **Primary contribution of Living Labs: enabling conditions for change**
The ToC models implied that Living Labs most reliably generated **enabling conditions** for change, such as building relationships between key actors, and fostering learning, coordination, and producing usable evidence, rather than direct territorial transformation within the scope of individual projects.

While the ToC models explained how change was expected to happen ex ante, they did not capture the extent to which evidence was actually taken up and integrated into policy processes. This gap is addressed in the next section, which examines policy impact pathways and the extent to which experiment-generated knowledge can become policy learning and lead to adaptation in practice.

3.3 3.3 Pathways to policy impact

The preceding section described five thematic Theory of Change (ToC) models developed and implemented by the LLs as part of their data experiments. These models illustrated how data experiments were expected to operate by linking short- and longer-term outcomes, while identifying targeted policy actions and considering potential risks that could arise during implementation. The ToCs were underpinned by set of assumptions that captured different types of hypotheses, ranging from operational (e.g. stakeholders engagement in data collection), to policy relevance (e.g. the use of fine-grained data to inform future funding), and to broader transition dynamics (e.g. the role of local natural resources in driving territorial value creation).

Building on this work, this section examines how the evidence generated through the LL experiments can be interpreted in policy terms and brought forward. While the ToC models provided insight into how rural transitions were expected to occur through coherent experimental

logics using new data and tools, the following analysis focuses on what the insights obtained towards the end of the experiments imply for policy learning and potential policy adaptation.

Three policy impact pathways are used as an analytical lens: cross-sectoral integration, territorially sensitive resource allocation, and governance and collaboration. These pathways reflect core principles of place-based policymaking and provide a framework for examining how experimental evidence reveals policy challenges and potential directions for change. While analytically distinct, these pathways are often jointly relevant in practice, and individual LLs may contribute to more than one pathway depending on their experimental focus and governance context.

This step took place towards the end of the experimental process. At the outset, LLs mapped existing policies and initiatives into policy panoramas to assess the extent to which they addressed or constrained the identified transition challenges (see Section 3.1). Building on this, some LLs designed their experiments and ToC in close alignment with specific policy frameworks (such as [Galicia](#), [Monmouthshire](#), [North Karelia](#)), while others adopted a more exploratory approach without a single, clearly defined policy. At this stage of the experimental process, informed by the evidence generated, each LL identified a key policy or combination of policy instruments to which the experimental evidence is relevant and from which implications for policy learning and adaptation could be drawn. A summary of the policies identified, and the governmental levels involved is provided in Table 6.

Table 6: Key policies relevant to the experimental evidence and the governmental levels involved

Pilot Region	Key policy(ies) targeted	Governmental levels involved in targeted policy(ies)
Galicia	Model Settlements	Regional (Galicia) and Local municipal authorities along with private landowners
Garfagnana	Local Development Strategies drawing on CAP & Cohesion Policy, in conjunction with nature/climate-related policies incl. carbon credits and Natura 2000	EU; regional level (Tuscany); municipalities and other local public entities; owners of forested land, forest consortia, cooperatives, and local associations; private forested-land owners
Gloucestershire	Local service commissioning and provision; Digital Infrastructure, Inclusion and Innovation Strategy (DIIS)	Local authorities (e.g. Gloucestershire County Council) operate as service commissioners with decision-making authority and resources; local third sector Voluntary, Community and Social Enterprise organisations (VCSEs) deliver community-based services incl. digital inclusion
Mazowieckie /Radomski subregion	Development Strategy of the Mazowieckie Voivodship; Local development strategy of the LAG Razem na Piaskowcu; Strategy	EU; Regional (Mazowieckie Voivodship) and Local municipal authorities; Mazovian Regional Tourism Organization (MROT)

	of the Mazovian Regional Tourism Organization (MROT)	
Monmouthshire	Well-being of Future Generations (Wales) Act	National level (Wales), with local assessments of well-being on the basis of which regional Public Service Boards (PSB) prepare and implement plans to improve well-being
Nockregion-Oberkärnten	A set of policy instruments including LEADER (LDS and flagship project 'Best living and working region' under CAP); Regional Development Framework (RDF)	Policies operate across multiple governance levels, including EU; regional (State of Carinthia, RDF); local and functional area (municipalities and LAG Nockregion-Oberkärnten, LDS, RDF)
North Karelia	National Integration Act Reform making municipalities responsible for the planning, development and monitoring of immigrants' integration at the local level	National (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment); regional public bodies including ELY, Regional Council of North Karelia, Employment services; local municipal authorities incl. dedicated municipal immigration coordinators
Osona/Sant Miquel de Balenyà	Municipal urban planning; Urban development/renewal measures e.g. via Barcelona Provincial Council funding schemes; broader regional or national planning initiatives esp. in transport, infrastructure and air quality	Experiment sits at the local level with primary public body responsible for urban planning being the municipal administration, however, interrelated planning decisions and funding opportunities are located at regional/provincial (Barcelona Provincial Council) and national level
Osrednjeslovenska	CAP (LEADER/CLLD in particular)	EU; National and Local/functional areas (LAGs)
Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara	in the intersection of water, rural (CAP) and broader regional development incl. Cohesion Policy (esp. infrastructure and innovation)	Experiment sits at the provincial level; water management sits across vertical layers (EU; national; regional; provincial; municipal), horizontal/thematic layers (environment, agriculture), historical institutions (irrigation consortia, reclamation bodies) and legacy infrastructures (dams; reservoirs; canals)
Rhein-Hunsrück	District Development Concept (KEK), CAP (LEADER/CLLD in particular), Concept for career guidance, State's Youth and skilled labour strategies	EU; State (Rhineland-Palatinate); local/functional area levels (municipal authorities and LAG)
Świętokrzyskie	Key targeted policy is the Development Strategy of the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship	EU; regional (Marshal's Office of the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship; Regional Tourism Organization (ROT))

	2030+, other instruments also relevant such as LEADER / CLLD, national Cohesion Policy programmes such as Operational programme for Infrastructure, Climate and Environment (FEnIKS) (tourism and culture component)	
Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin	Local development strategy drawing on CAP/LEADER and national Cohesion Policy programmes such as Operational Programme for the Environment, Human Resources Development, Education, and Competitiveness and Innovation in Enterprises;	EU; National (Ministry of Agriculture and Food, Ministry of Tourism other MAs) and Local level/functional areas (municipal authorities and LAG)
Zaječar	Local rural development programmes; Local tourism strategies	EU (IPA funds); national level (Ministry of Agriculture, Chamber of Commerce); local self-governments and LAGs; tourism organisations

3.3.1 Pathway 1: Cross-sectoral integration

(Nonexhaustive examples include: *Garfagnana, Gloucestershire, Mazowieckie, Rhein-Hunsrück, Świętokrzyskie, Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin, Zaječar*)

The first pathway includes cases where evidence, analysis, and interpretation generated through the experiments made visible the cross-sectoral interdependencies underpinning territorial transitions. Across cases, the experiments suggested that rural assets generate value through multiple sectors, activities, and forms of value creation, while existing policy frameworks tended to approach them through fragmented sectoral interventions. The insights further indicated that challenges stemmed from the absence of a strategic territorial approach that combined multiple instruments of different nature and scales - such as regulations, certification schemes, awareness-raising measures, and subsidies - and mobilised different funding mechanisms.

This pathway is particularly prominent in cases where relevant policies were being implemented but had not yet responded effectively to the multi-faceted character of the challenges and opportunities facing the territory. A key feature of the experiments within this pathway is the collection of granular territorial data that reveal the multi-dimensional nature of the issue and point to the need for integrated solutions. This was often enabled through the engagement of a more diverse set of stakeholders, including actors from rural areas and groups not typically involved in policy design and implementation. Their involvement helped reveal different perspectives, as well as missing synergies and fragmentations across sectoral actors and policy measures.

For LLs falling under this pathway, a strong starting point was not how to refine individual policy instruments, but rather how to use territorial data to develop a more holistic problem definition that made new solutions conceivable. On this basis, the need for coordinated policy change across different domains became apparent. This is illustrated by the cases of [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) and [Zaječar](#), where data collection began with the exploration of a territorial asset - local food produce - and revealed that its strategic value was under-recognised. Similar patterns emerged in other LLs, although the specific assets differed. In the case of food production, the experiments showed that this asset was primarily addressed within the agricultural domain, notably through CAP support for production and partially processing. This reflected a predominantly sectoral approach to its use for socio-economic development, rather than a territorial one. Similarly, tourism strategies tended to emphasise investments in infrastructure, accommodation, and natural or cultural assets, with limited recognition of local food as a driver of tourism development.

The experiments further showed that territorial assets generate value through interdependencies spanning multiple sectors, activities, and forms of value creation. Several data experiments (e.g. [Zaječar](#), [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), [Świętokrzyskie](#), [Mazowieckie](#), [Garfagnana](#)) showed that a range of sectors contributed to the economic, social, environmental and cultural use of local assets, yet these were not recognised as part of a coherent system. For instance, beyond food production, the analysis in [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) and [Zaječar](#) identified the presence, and in some cases absence, of food processing facilities, as well as linkages to gastronomy, hospitality services, tourism, place identity, and the cultural sector. The data revealed interdependencies between sectors such as agricultural production, processing capacity, and demand from tourism and gastronomy, highlighting their combined potential to transform local produce into broader territorial value. A similar dynamic was observed in [Mazowieckie](#), where the experiment revealed connections not only to tourism, but also to art, crafts, interior design and therapeutic practices. Overall, the experiments demonstrated that the territorial value of local assets did not emerge from a single sector alone, but from the interaction between multiple activities, actors, and forms of value creation.

Making these sectoral interdependencies more visible also highlighted how existing policy frameworks continue to address them in isolation. This supported the identification of policy avenues that could enable integrated territorial solutions. One such avenue was the combination of measures financed through different operational programmes and funding sources. The experiments in [Zaječar](#) and [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) suggested that no single funding instrument could support the full range of activities involved, from production and processing to employment, skills, and market development. In this context, there was a need to make more effective use of territorial instruments such as LEADER to support integrated projects that combined funding from multiple sources, for example, linking employment measures (e.g. through ESF-funded programmes under Cohesion Policy) with support for farmers' organisations and production under the CAP. In this sense, the experiments pointed to the importance of coordinating existing instruments and funding streams around territorially embedded development objectives.

A related avenue concerned the strategic integration of sectors within regional development frameworks. The experiment in [Świętokrzyskie](#) pointed to the potential of approaches that brought together domains such as tourism, rural development, social inclusion, transport, and

environmental protection, thereby enabling more coherent responses to territorially embedded opportunities in the rural parts of the Voivodship.

The data experiments further indicated that rural transitions could be constrained by regulatory and administrative frameworks that were insufficiently adapted to territorially embedded and diversified forms of production. Regulatory and certification levers emerged as particularly important in shaping an enabling environment, as they influenced the capacity of local actors to diversify production, formalise activities, and generate territorial value. At the same time, existing national declaration systems (e.g. in Bulgaria) did not always adequately accommodate diversified and small-scale production practices, including forms of organic and artisanal production. This created disincentives and limited the ability of local actors to fully benefit from available support schemes. The findings therefore point to the need for regulatory frameworks that are better aligned with the realities of diversified and small-scale production systems, while also highlighting the limited influence that local and regional actors may have over nationally determined regulatory arrangements.

Furthermore, the design of relevant regulations needs to take into account the **cultural context of embedded informal practices** that contribute to the solidarity economy. This highlights a trade-off between the need for formal regulatory requirements for food production in smallholdings and the presence of informal production practices, which can limit the scaling of local food systems. The design of rules for smallholdings, food safety in specific, therefore needs to support a **gradual transition from informal to formal activities**. In this regard, the experiments in [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) and [Zaječar](#) highlighted that **such transition depended on enhancing relational factors such as trust** among actors, further discussed under the governance pathway.

Overall, RUSTIK LLs falling under this pathway demonstrated that rural assets generated value through interdependencies spanning multiple sectors, activities, and forms of value creation. Existing policy frameworks, however, tended to fragment these interdependencies into separate sectoral interventions, thereby constraining their contribution to socio-demographic and environmental transitions. The pathway therefore points to the need for territorially coordinated policy and governance approaches capable of aligning interventions across sectors and scales. The box below summarises how the evidence generated through the LL experiments identified specific areas where policy adaptation may be required under this pathway.

- **Recognising multi-dimensional territorial value:** Rural territorial assets often generate multiple forms of value, including economic, social, cultural, and environmental, across interconnected sectors. Rural and regional policy frameworks, and their support measures, tend to address these assets through sector-specific or single-objective interventions. This points to an avenue for policy adaptation through **approaches that recognise and support the multiple forms of value associated with local assets**, for instance by designing integrated interventions that link sectors such as agriculture, tourism, culture and local identity within a shared territorial framework.

- **Aligning the policy mix:** The development of integrated solutions depends on combining multiple policy instruments with different functions and governance levels. Alongside financial support, regulatory frameworks (e.g. for smallholdings; small enterprises), certification schemes (e.g. for organic farming and artisanal products), infrastructure investment (e.g. processing and logistics), and market development measures (e.g. territorial branding) all play distinct roles. This requires coordination mechanisms that bring these instruments together around shared territorial objectives
- **Funding combination:** Implementation is facilitated when funding from multiple sources can be combined to support integrated local interventions. This includes aligning and jointly mobilising instruments such as CAP (e.g. support to farmers' organisations and production), and regional development funds such as ESF (e.g. skills and employment measures). This suggests the need for territorial mechanisms such as LEADER/CLLD and regulations that enable coordinated use of funding across programmes and sectors.
- **Regulatory adaptation:** This includes adjusting CAP declaration requirements to better accommodate diversified and small-scale production systems, including organic farming, and support their links to gastronomy and tourism, where relevant.
- **Local enabling measures:** Within this broader policy mix, local authorities can support cross-sectoral solutions through non-subsidy measures such as marketing tools, tax incentives, deregulation, and reducing administrative burden. These measures can facilitate the interaction between sectors and complement other policy instruments, while strengthening the role of local authorities.
- **Capacity building:** Cross-sectoral integration depends on awareness of interdependencies between sectors (e.g. agriculture and tourism) and the functioning of value chains. This suggests the need for capacity-building efforts at local level.

3.3.2 Pathway 2: Territorialisation and allocation pathway

(Nonexhaustive examples include *Galicia, Gloucestershire, Monmouthshire, Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara, Sant Miquel de Balenyà (Osona), Osrednjeslovenska*)

Pathway 2 focuses on territorialisation and resource allocation through differentiated treatment of places. Under this pathway, data experiments demonstrated that uniform resource allocation and standardised instruments were misaligned with territorially specific needs and challenges.

Where this pathway is prominent, most LLs had an existing policy, law or sectoral service in view from the outset of the experiment. The data experiments were often designed with the intention to refine their design or implementation by addressing assumed evidence gaps. These choices were grounded in two main considerations. In some cases, experiments were based on the assumption that existing implementation or service delivery did not adequately capture territorial needs or sufficiently target resources. This prompted the use of data approaches to reveal disparities, as seen in *Gloucestershire, Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara, and Sant Miquel de Balenyà*. In

other cases, design choices were driven by more practical considerations: limited public resources required clearer evidence on where interventions should be prioritised, as illustrated in Galicia. In some LLs, such as [Monmouthshire](#), both rationales were present. In the case of [Osrednjeslovenska](#), the focus was less on spatial disparities and more on integrating social dimensions into local project assessment and resource allocation.

Insights into fairer and more place-sensitive resource allocation were prominently pursued through experiments that combined quantitative and qualitative data, in some cases triangulating the two, or using them in a complementary way. Methods such as participatory mapping, citizen surveys, and GIS analysis were employed to make visible and compare needs and challenges that existing policies either failed to address or could have addressed more effectively through improved territorial targeting/tailoring. Data tools that allow spatial comparison based on multiple datasets and criteria - through composite indices and dashboards - are particularly relevant to this pathway as well.

Several examples illustrate this. In [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#), policy actions, identified in the ToC, prominently targeted the municipal urban plan, a spatial planning instrument considered outdated, alongside urban renewal actions. The experiment had a strong spatial component and developed a Quality-of-Life (QoL) Index providing a comparative spatial overview across the neighbourhoods of [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#). The index was particularly relevant given the area's increasing population and existing socio-spatial dynamics, which risked reinforcing disparities, alongside existing environmental challenges such as air quality. By **combining objective and subjective indicators**, the composite index showed that **quality of life varied across neighbourhoods and was associated with differences in the quality of the built environment**. This territorial variation reflected a concentration of low quality-of-life scores in more deprived areas. As a result, applying the index helped to **identify where interventions to improve quality of life were most needed**, providing policymakers with evidence for strategic territorial targeting. The results also pointed to the **need to refine eligibility criteria** for funding urban improvements, enabling resources to be allocated in ways that **better reflect intra-municipal disparities**.

A related topic of liveability and place attractiveness, particularly for young people (aged 16-44), was explored in [Monmouthshire](#) to better understand how to attract or retain this demographic group. The experiment was designed with the Welsh Well-being of Future Generations Act in mind, seeking to contribute evidence to the multiannual assessment process that informs planned improvements under the Act. Rather than relying solely on objective indicators, the experiment centred on **how territorial inequalities and opportunities were experienced in practice**. It examined how younger people perceived access to services and opportunities for education and employment under existing arrangements. To do so, it relied on **qualitative, georeferenced data to capture territorial differences in lived experience**. The findings highlighted, in particular, the impact of limited public transport infrastructure on liveability for younger rural residents, as well as **variations in perceptions across different parts of the county**.

Together, these cases suggest that territorial disparities are not fully captured through structural indicators alone and that integrating qualitative and experiential forms of evidence can **inform more nuanced territorial responses** and tailored policy targeting, for example through town-based regeneration plans, as illustrated by the case of Monmouthshire.

While the previous case highlighted the role of qualitative, georeferenced data, the [Gloucestershire](#) LL takes a different entry point but also contributes to this pathway. It followed a strong governance logic by developing and testing an analytical tool (dashboard) aimed at strengthening the capacity of rural service delivery organisations to reduce digital inequality. At the same time, by bringing together spatially referenced data from service delivery organisations and public registries, the tool enabled an initial, comparative view of the intensity, overlap, and gaps in service provision across the county. This revealed **disparities in digital connectivity and access to support**, as well as **underserved population groups**, particularly low-income and older residents. Interpreted in policy terms, these emerging insights highlight limitations in current approaches to digital inclusion. In particular, they point to **fragmented and incompatible datasets across public authorities and service providers**, which constrain the ability to identify need, target interventions spatially, and coordinate service delivery effectively. As a result, **existing funding schemes and support initiatives risk not reaching the areas and populations most in need**.

The findings suggests that fragmented data environments contribute to territorial targeting challenges and point to the **need for adaptations in both data use and resource allocation**. This includes strengthening data integration through more coherent data environments and cross-departmental standards, as well as refining funding formulas and eligibility criteria to better reflect differentiated territorial conditions, including higher per-unit costs of service provision in rural areas. More broadly, the case highlights the importance of addressing **intersecting dimensions of digital exclusion** - including connectivity, access to equipment, digital skills and confidence, and wider socio-economic vulnerabilities - through **funding criteria and support schemes that combine these factors** to better identify and target vulnerable populations.

The [Osrednjeslovenska](#) LL related to this pathway from a somewhat different angle, focusing on food waste and redistribution, social inclusion, and community-based services. In the course of the experiment, limitations in existing project assessment approaches within local support schemes such as CLLD were identified, particularly their limited capacity to capture social value and qualitative community impacts. As a practical policy-oriented output, the experiment pointed towards the potential value of developing a template that could help LAGs integrate such dimensions more systematically into project selection processes.

This pathway also operates at higher territorial scales, as shown by the LL in [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#) (Emilia-Romagna Region). The case is illustrative of the territorial allocation pathway, as the analysis identified differentiated territorial contexts and intervention needs across and within provinces. Similar to other cases, this required the collection and geo-referenced analysis of multi-sectoral data – in this case from agriculture, hydrology and infrastructure. While in western Emilia-Romagna (Piacenza and Parma) the experiment identified lack of reservoirs and water irrigation shortages, existing investment sources were limited to expansion basins designed for flood control. The findings suggest implications for how existing EU-supported regional and rural development frameworks distribute funding. In particular, the experiment highlights the need for greater flexibility in tailoring interventions on the ground, including greater flexibility in the scope of eligible measures and in eligibility criteria, enabling different places to pursue context-specific water management interventions.

Overall, RUSTIK LLs falling under this pathway demonstrate that standardised policy instruments and resource allocation frameworks may fail to capture differentiated territorial conditions, lived experiences, and intersecting vulnerabilities, affecting capacities to respond to transitions. Across cases, the experiments showed that combining quantitative, qualitative, georeferenced, and multi-source territorial data could make previously under-recognised disparities and needs more visible, thereby supporting more place-sensitive targeting of resources and tailoring of measures. The findings further suggest that effective territorialisation may require adaptations not only in funding allocation, but also in evidence systems, eligibility criteria, and the flexibility of implementation frameworks to respond to differentiated territorial contexts. The box below summarises how the evidence generated through the LL experiments points to areas where policy adaptation may be required under this pathway.

- **Integrating qualitative territorial evidence:** Georeferenced qualitative insights can capture dimensions of liveability and place-attractiveness not reflected in structural indicators, particularly in relation to demographic transitions and youth retention. This points to an avenue for policy adaptation through **the integration of qualitative and subjective evidence** on liveability, along with quantitative metrics to **support more tailored targeting of resources, for instance through town-based regeneration plans.**
- **Accounting for structural territorial differences:** Standard digital service-related allocation mechanisms often do not reflect structurally higher per-unit costs of service provision in certain territorial contexts, particularly in rural and low-density areas. Avenues for policy adaptation go through adjustments to funding models and allocation criteria that better account for territorial cost differentials. In parallel, eligibility criteria for digital capacity initiatives may need to consider multiple and intersecting barriers to access (connectivity, equipment availability, digital confidence, and broader socio-economic vulnerabilities).
- **Increasing flexibility in funding frameworks:** Standardised funding measures often do not align with diverse territorial needs and territorial assets (e.g. funding prioritising flood control investments, while some areas face challenges with irrigation shortages). This limits the opportunity to draw on available funding mechanisms like LEADER/CLLD or Cohesion Policy to address context-specific challenges and potentials. **Greater flexibility in the scope of eligible interventions and eligibility criteria** can enable different areas within rural regions to nuance responses accordingly.
- **Embedding evidence in allocation processes:** Territorial evidence is more likely to influence policy where it can be **integrated into existing multiannual assessment cycles** and where territorial instruments provide **mechanisms to prioritise interventions based on emerging evidence during implementation.** This points to the need to align evidence

generation and dissemination with institutional decision-making processes, which is explored further in the Decentralised Rural Proofing section of this report.

3.3.3 Pathway 3: Inclusive governance and collaboration

(Elements evident to a varying degree in all LLs; illustrative examples from [Galicia](#); [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#); [North Karelia](#); [Mazowieckie](#); [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#); [Rhein-Hunsrück](#); [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#); [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#); [Zaječar](#))

The cross-sectoral and territorial resource allocation pathways highlighted the need to integrate policies across domains and to adapt interventions and resources to place-specific conditions. By contrast, the governance pathway emphasises that the effectiveness of solutions depends not only on the design of evidence-based policy instruments, but also on the capacity of governance systems to coordinate actors, build trust, and enable participation across different levels and sectors. Drawing on the broader institutional context identified in the Transition Narratives (see Section 3.1), the experimental data provided more specific insights into how governance conditions shaped the implementation of solutions in practice. This included identifying coordination gaps, relevant actors, and the mechanisms required to address them. In some cases, they also directly contributed to addressing these gaps through the development of data tools, coordination mechanisms, and capacities that strengthened governance arrangements.

Across the LLs, governance learning and possible implications ranged from recognising which actors were most relevant, to understanding how they could be effectively engaged, and how their interactions could be coordinated to address shared challenges. This included the need for coordination at the scale at which these challenges or territorial assets operated. These insights are reflected in the four points below.

First, a number of experiments contributed to governance by **making previously under-recognised actors visible and recognising forms of contribution and knowledge** that existing governance arrangements had tended to overlook. This was partly enabled by incorporating mapping activities into the ToC, which complemented the initial Institutional Mapping exercise undertaken in Cycle 1. Moreover, to obtain more granular, inclusive and holistic qualitative data, many experiments utilised methods such as local dialogues or workshops. These approaches engaged actors or citizens who often fell outside formal policy processes, participatory mechanisms or coordination platforms and partnerships, which typically operated at higher governance levels or remained narrower in scope. In this way, some experiments had already, within their lifespan, played an important role in connecting these actors to existing local structures such as LAGs, and in facilitating long-term engagement to support strategic planning.

Some data experiments were positioned to contribute to governance adaptation through the **more formalised inclusion of previously under-recognised actors in strategic governance and resource allocation**. A particularly explicit example was [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#), where the experiment's ToC aimed to use data to demonstrate the policy relevance of small rural businesses (SRBs), particularly one-person businesses, for the rural fabric, including their role in maintaining local infrastructure and economic activity. This took place in a context where the regional agency, as a platform for regional development, also acting as a LAG, had been actively promoting greater understanding and, where possible, alignment of diverse sectoral interests.

At the same time, the quantitative evidence that demonstrated the scale and contribution of SRBs to local liveability and well-being provided new insights for governance structures beyond the LAG.

These included the local administrations, the Economic Chamber of Carinthia Region, and the Tourism association operating at an inter-municipal/functional scale. This illustrated how the experiment supported the visibility of previously under-represented rural actors at different territorial tiers, opening new avenues for their inclusion in different development processes.

The increased visibility of these actors and their added value, along with their needs, further supported their recognition in strategic instruments and processes such as the future Regional Development Vision of the Land of Carinthia and municipal integrated community planning, as well as their engagement in funding frameworks such as LEADER.

At the same time, qualitative evidence highlighted important constraints affecting the ability of SRBs to participate in governance. Limited time, staffing, and financial resources restricted their engagement in strategic planning and decision-making processes. This suggests that effective governance change requires not only recognising such actors through data but also providing appropriate structures through which they can engage collectively, as noted in the ToC. In this case, this was exemplified by the flagship LEADER initiative undertaken by the LAG [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#), *Best Living and Working Region*, which articulated a shared vision for the region and its development. The initiative integrated evidence from RUSTIK, positioning small businesses as the backbone of the regional economy, and brought together municipalities and businesses to strengthen networks among SRBs and support their collective engagement.

Second, some experiments strengthened governance capacity at the local level by providing tools that enabled public bodies to generate, compare and use evidence for decision-making. This was evident in several LLs including [North Karelia](#), where the experiment developed, through an iterative process involving governmental bodies at different levels, a survey to assess the well-being and integration of immigrants across 13 municipalities. This equipped local authorities with a structured tool (the survey) to systematically incorporate bottom-up evidence from service users into decision-making. This directly addressed a recognised capacity gap. Following the transfer of responsibility for integration services to municipalities in 2025, local authorities lacked consistent data and tools to monitor needs and performance. The survey enabled them to collect evidence on service use and usefulness directly from service users, supporting more informed targeting and prioritisation of local interventions. **In this sense, governance capacity is shaped by the availability of tools and mechanisms that enable evidence-informed decision-making.** This capacity is **reinforced through the institutionalisation of such tools**, which ensures their continued use beyond the lifetime of a project and embeds them in regular governance practice. This was illustrated in the [North Karelia case](#), where the Regional Council took ownership of the tool. By grounding decisions in the experiences and needs of immigrants, the tool also supported more inclusive forms of governance.

Third, several LLs generated valuable institutional learning, particularly regarding how participation, trust, and local leadership shaped planning and implementation processes. In [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#), participatory tools such as photo elicitation and georeferenced surveys provided accessible ways to engage citizens in planning processes, helping to build stronger community support for initiatives related to the built environment and quality of life. While not the primary aim of the experiment, such engagement also had the potential to strengthen citizenship by empowering residents to take civic action where policy responses were limited. In [Galicia](#), the

experiment provided insights into how governance arrangements functioned in practice, and which factors were critical for their success. The focus was on the regional government instrument known as the Model Settlement, which required a voluntary agreement between the regional government, local authorities, and the local population, supported by at least 70 percent of residents. In this context, trust proved essential. The LL observed that trust and support were often facilitated by respected local community leaders who mobilised landowners and enabled dialogue. For municipal authorities, the ability to identify and work with such local leaders or gatekeepers therefore became a key element in enabling successful participation. **The experiments therefore highlight that effective participation depends not only on the existence of formal participatory mechanisms, but also on relational factors such as trust, legitimacy, local leadership, and accessibility.**

A **fourth** direction of the governance pathway emerges from the recognition that territorial transitions generate coordination needs that often extend across administrative, sectoral, and organisational boundaries, and therefore require coordination at the scale at which territorial assets and systems operate.

Because LL experiments relied heavily on the collection of data from diverse networks, they often brought together actors who held different forms of knowledge about the issue being explored. The process of data collection therefore became an opportunity for joint problem framing, where stakeholders collectively reflected on the nature of the challenge and possible approaches for addressing it. In several cases, **this process revealed interdependencies** between actors, sectors and territories, and highlighted the importance of dialogue and coordination. The findings suggest that effective coordination in territorially embedded transitions may depend on governance arrangements that support trusted and secure forms of information exchange, enabling actors to develop shared understandings of interdependencies, collective risks, and coordination needs.

Coordination challenges become particularly visible in contexts where natural resources, ecosystems, labour markets, or other territorial assets extend across administrative boundaries and require collective management. This was evident in the case of [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#), where the experiment demonstrated how interdependencies within the hydrological system created coordination needs across water management actors and administrative boundaries. The data highlighted the role of governance in potential solutions, particularly the need to strengthen coordination in water withdrawal and water release. It also revealed where coordination mattered most, including across different types of water management consortia and administrative boundaries, as such coordination could help reduce the risk of stress on the hydrological system. Similar dynamics emerged in [Mazowieckie](#) and [Zaječar](#), where shared territorial assets across municipalities highlighted the rationale for more cooperative and regionalised approaches to economic development and territorial branding. The Mazowieckie LL additionally pointed to the importance of intermediaries, particularly NGOs, in strengthening coordination and networks between municipalities, public institutions, and entrepreneurs.

Governance arrangements that support more permanent or institutionalised horizontal coordination are also crucial when transition solutions operate within a constellation of sectoral and governmental systems that may function in a fragmented way. Coordination gaps may vary depending on the context. For instance, in [Rhein-Hunsrück](#), gaps existed between schools,

employers, youth organisations, and labour market stakeholders. In [Trojan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), gaps were observed across the food value chain, including smallholdings, processors, hospitality providers, and local authorities. These gaps are compounded by the absence of structures with the mandate and capacity to support sustained dialogue at the appropriate scale.

The findings point to the need for governance arrangements that support horizontal coordination, for example through local partnerships or platforms. Such governance adaptations to support horizontal cooperation, however, depend on several factors, including **clarity on institutional responsibility** (identifying actors capable of and willing to drive coordination), **human capital** (skills, knowledge, organisational capacity), and **financial resources**. Where such enabling conditions are weak or absent, governance gaps may emerge between the increasing need for coordination around territorially embedded transitions and the capacity of existing actors to fulfil this role. At the time of writing, these capacities are not equally present across regions. For instance, the LAG in [Trojan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), a potential intermediary that could coordinate actions for the creation of a territorial brand, lacks the organisational, logistical, and knowledge capacity to create, manage, or sustain such a collective initiative. Similarly, existing associations and business networks in [Zaječar](#) report inability to coordinate actions related to the promotion and visibility of local food and products. This reveals a **governance gap between the need for coordination and the capacity of existing actors to fulfil this role**, pointing to the **importance of strengthening intermediary structures such as LAGs or business networks**.

Overall, RUSTIK LLs falling under this pathway demonstrate that effective territorial transitions require governance capacities that complement policy instruments and evidence generation by sustaining coordination, participation, trust, and collective action across actors, sectors, and territories. The experiments revealed governance gaps linked to fragmented institutional arrangements, limited intermediary capacity, insufficient coordination mechanisms, and difficulties in maintaining long-term cooperation at appropriate territorial scales. The pathway therefore points towards governance approaches that strengthen horizontal coordination, intermediary structures, participatory capacities, and trusted mechanisms for collective problem framing and data sharing. The box below summarises how the evidence generated through the LL experiments points to areas where governance adaptation is already emerging or may be required under this pathway.

- **Governance as an entry point:** In several cases, experimental evidence shows that transition challenges are constrained less by the absence of policy instruments than by limitations in governance arrangements. This suggests that policy adaptation may need to focus on governance itself as a primary entry point for action.
- **Collective organisation:** Some rural actors such as one-person businesses and smallholdings often have more limited capacity to engage in strategic process and publicly funded projects and are therefore less visible within governance systems. At the same time, data on their scale and contribution can make them visible as a group and support the development of coordination structures, such as networks or

LEADER-led initiatives. This indicates the **role of territorial instruments in enabling dispersed actors to organise and engage collectively.**

- **Incentivising collective action:** While instruments such as LEADER/CLLD have the potential to support community-based projects, **the design of their calls or support schemes varies across countries**, and in some cases continues to prioritise individual support aligned with local strategies. As a result, cooperation among actors is not systematically incentivised. This points to an avenue for policy adaptation through funding models that more consistently encourage collective initiatives. **This may include designing eligibility criteria or calls that require or reward collaboration/partnerships across actors, sectors, or territories.**
- **Sustained coordination/interaction structures:** In the absence of mechanisms that support sustained interaction, responses may remain fragmented and collective initiatives are difficult to initiate or maintain. **Where no actor has the mandate, capacity, or incentive to lead long-term**, cross-sectoral initiatives such as territorial branding, youth retention, or shared resource management **are unlikely to be sustained.** This suggests the need for governance structures that give space to make stakeholder interdependencies visible and sustain dialogue as a basis of cooperation.
- **Mandated coordination at functional scale:** The interdependencies and cooperation needs revealed through such interactions may extend beyond a single municipality or administrative region. Implementation of transition solutions adapted to local assets requires a clearly mandated coordinating actor at the scale at which the asset or system operates. In such context, coordination needs may often arise at a scale that does not correspond to a single administration or a single region. This indicates the need to assign or strengthen coordination roles aligned with functional territories. Public authorities at local or regional level may need to assume this role or reinforce the capacity of intermediary actors (e.g. LAGs, community organisations, business networks) with dedicated responsibilities and resources.
- Local level capacity to coordinate service delivery can be strengthened through iteratively developed tools such as surveys and dashboards – upper levels need to support the development and institutionalisation of such tools.

Table 7 summarises the three policy impact pathways, distinguishing between their core characteristics, grounded in LL experiences, and the types of evidence and analytical signals through which these elements become visible in data experiments.

Table 7: Policy impact pathways and their empirical manifestation in the RUSTIK data experiments

Pathway	What the pathway reveals?	How it becomes visible?	Where the key policy implication lies?
Cross-sectoral integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sectoral silos; sectoral over territorial logic in policy measures; • Strategic value of under-recognised sectors and assets; • Multiple forms of territorial value generated by local assets • How sectoral policy objectives interact in specific places; • Need to align sectoral objectives and instruments around place-based challenges and opportunities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence about under-recognised sectors and their role in local systems; • Data (often qualitative) showing interactions and interdependencies across sectors; • Analyses revealing trade-offs or potential sectoral synergies in specific territories; • Qualitative evidence of fragmented or misaligned policy responses across sectors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy frameworks need to coherently address the multiple forms of territorial value generated through interactions across sectors and actors; • Cross-sectoral integration often requires intermediary structures or governance arrangements capable of coordinating actors and instruments across sectors.
Territorialisation and resource allocation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial disparities across areas within territories and between population groups; • The need to enhance territorial targeting or prioritisation of resources; • How to combine multiple forms of evidence to support territorial prioritisation and targeting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative evidence of territorially differentiated needs across areas or demographic groups; • Qualitative evidence of territorial differences in lived experiences (e.g. in fields of mobility, housing) • Evidence on which territories or groups benefit from or are underserved by existing funding streams; • Composite indicators (presented via indices; dashboards, decisions support systems) combining multiple dimensions to support territorial prioritisation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocation systems, eligibility criteria, and implementation frameworks need greater territorial sensitivity and flexibility. • Institutional capacity is required to translate territorial evidence into long-term strategic responses rather than predominantly day-to-day operational management.
Inclusive governance and collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under-recognised or under-represented actors; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated overview of relevant actors depending on the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding and eligibility models may need to incentivise

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragmented data environments across actors and governance structures; • Coordination needs emerging at functional territorial scales that may not correspond to existing administrative arrangements 	<p>sectoral interest of the LL;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence of participatory practices becoming embedded in governance and decision-making processes; • Evidence of weak or fragmented coordination across actors and levels; • Evidence on gaps in coordination responsibility and intermediary roles • Evidence on capacity constraints (skills, organisational resources) • Evidence on trust, local leadership and social capital as enabling or limiting factors. 	<p>collaboration across actors, sectors, and territories;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination may require mandated actors operating at functional territorial scales; • Strengthened intermediary structures and trusted information exchange are needed.
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3.4 3.4 Decentralised Rural Proofing

3.4.1 Background

The preceding section examined how experimental data generated by the Living Labs could be strategically mobilised to support policy learning and adaptation. It focussed on identifying the types of policy-relevant insights such data could provide, such as those related to sectoral interdependencies, resource allocation logics, or governance arrangements that enable coordination and collective action. The analysis moved from a context-specific understanding of what data and tools function in practice towards broader conclusions on how existing policy instruments could be adapted in line with core place-based principles, including cross-sectoral integration, territorially sensitive resource allocation, and enabling governance. In this sense, the logic progressed from bottom-up experimental learning to its implications for policy. This previous pathway section also informed the selection of concrete policies and policy mixes to be examined in the decentralised rural proofing pilots, by clarifying where experimental evidence was most closely connected to ongoing or forthcoming changes in strategies, programmes or legal frameworks.

By contrast, the policy rationale underpinning the following and final step, decentralised rural proofing, was explicit from the outset and was operationalised following the completion of the preceding steps. Rather than asking how experimental evidence might inform policy, decentralised rural proofing examined whether existing governance arrangements and data practices could support ongoing place-based rural proofing. It built on the mechanisms and

networks established within the LLs, as well as on the long-term outcomes identified during the experiments, the evidence generated, and the evolving policy priorities.

Conventional rural proofing is typically organised as a centralised, desk-based exercise conducted by national or regional authorities. This approach often struggles to fully capture the diversity of rural territories, differences in local governance contexts and the situated knowledge of rural actors. It also tends to focus primarily on avoiding negative impacts on rural areas, rather than exploring how rural resources and opportunities could more actively contribute to improved policy design. As a result, it may overlook small, targeted policy adjustments that could make a significant difference for rural communities.

In response, RUSTIK developed Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) as a complementary layer to these existing approaches. DRP brings elements of the proofing process closer to rural territories by engaging local and regional actors in focused, place-sensitive micro-assessments. These assessments examine how specific policies relate to rural needs, capacities and transition challenges. In doing so, DRP adds a bottom-up perspective that can channel local insights into policy processes and support more responsive, territorially attuned adjustments.

Earlier work in WP1 (RUSTIK D1.3, 2023) identified similar limitations in its review of national rural proofing arrangements and their local adaptations, noting that these approaches tend to remain largely centralised, desk-based and reliant on aggregated indicators, with limited scope for territorially differentiated analysis and routine engagement of local actors. Against this backdrop, the DRP pilots can be seen as a complementary response. Rather than proposing an additional comprehensive rural proofing framework, they apply decentralised, place-sensitive micro-assessments to explore how general rural proofing principles can be translated into concrete territorial practices and embedded within existing governance and data systems.

RUSTIK tested DRP through five Pilot Regions' Living Labs (LLs), which volunteered to act as pilots. Each DRP pilot acted as a decentralised setting where roles, data practices and assessment routines could be tested under real policy and governance conditions. Local and regional administrations, stakeholders, intermediaries and other knowledge holders worked together around a clearly defined proofing task, making visible how responsibilities, information and decision making are shared in practice. The pilots translated the general principles of DRP into concrete practices and generate insights into what kinds of DRP arrangements were workable in different territorial and institutional contexts. These pilots applied the DRP model described in the methodological section, using bottom-up micro-assessments and existing evidence to review how selected policies worked in rural contexts.

The following section examines five DRP pilots that operationalised this approach in different settings, illustrating how DRP micro-assessments and participation arrangements worked in practice. In this context, it also analyses the strategic role DRP can play in mainstreaming rural evidence into active policy development and discusses the institutional and data conditions needed for such decentralised proofing to be realistically maintained and scaled.

3.4.1 Profiles of the DRP pilots

The common Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) approach was tested across a wide range of transition challenges, policy foci and governance settings in the five DRP pilot cases. The pilots deliberately covered a diverse spectrum of rural policy contexts: from a digital inclusion strategy at the county level in [Gloucestershire](#) to the implementation of a national reform under the Integration Act in [North Karelia](#), and broader policy mixes relating to forestry in [Garfagnana](#), small rural businesses in [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#) and local food systems in [Trojan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#). Such diversity was intentional, as the pilot phase aimed not to test DRP in a single 'ideal' institutional context, but to explore how a common proofing logic operated across different policy domains, territorial challenges and organisational settings.

At the same time, the pilots differed not only in their thematic focus but also in their institutional anchoring. They were anchored in a range of organisations, including a research institute, a university, a regional council and LAG or intermediary based regional structures. As a result, they combined different forms of evidence and approaches to stakeholder engagement. Some pilots worked more directly with strategies of legal forms, while others applied DRP to broader policy mixes and territorially grounded development questions. Table 8 provides more than a descriptive overview: it shows the range of settings in which DRP was operationalised and establishes a comparative basis for the analysis that follows. More detailed, case-specific information is available in the fiches in Annex 2.

Table 8: Profiles of the DRP pilots (based on DRP pilot fiches in Annex 2)

Pilot region	Transition and policy focus	Actors and methods
Garfagnana (IT)	Mountain region facing population decline and ageing: the DRP pilot examined whether forestry-related policy mixes support climate transition and community regeneration.	Led by CREA with LAG, municipal and regional actors: combining evidence review with stakeholder consultations and dialogue with regional authorities.
Gloucestershire (UK)	Predominantly rural county with a digital transition challenge: the DRP pilot reviewed how the emerging digital inclusion strategy and related plans address rural-urban gaps in connectivity, skills and access to services.	Led by CCRI with the county council and advisory group: using an online survey, workshop, expert interviews and rapid review of related policy documents.
Nockregion-Oberkärnten (AT)	Shrinking and ageing rural region: the DRP pilot focused on how regional strategies and funding instruments reflect the role and needs of small rural businesses.	Coordinated by BAB with the regional association, LAG and business representatives: to process through interviews, questionnaires, synthesis of written material and feedback discussions.

North Karelia (FI)	Peripheral region facing demographic decline and labour shortages: the DRP pilot assessed the implementation of the Integration Act reform and its implications for municipal integration services and immigrant retention.	Led by the Regional Council with the regional state authority and municipalities: using semi-structured interviews, a reflection workshop and a web-based immigrant survey.
Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin (BG)	Rural area undergoing socio-economic transition: the DRP pilot explored a food-related policy mix and the role of local food in territorial development and value retention.	Led by Sofia University with the LAG and local actors: combining GIS-based analysis, workshops, interviews, an online questionnaire and observations of food festivals.

Taken together, the overview shows that, despite the diversity of policy and governance contexts, a recognisable common DRP logic emerged. Differences primary lay in the institutional anchoring of the process, the specific policy entry points, and the ways in which evidence and stakeholder participation were combined in each case.

3.4.2 Decentralised rural proofing as a governance mechanism

In the pilots, decentralised rural proofing (DRP) **operated as a governance mechanism that connected local micro-assessments to multi-level policy processes**. Building on the DRP steps outlined in the methodology (see Section 2), from defining scope, objectives and actors, through formulating guiding questions and preparing evidence, to conducting micro-assessments and feeding back findings, this section examines how DRP translated local experience into policy learning and embedded this learning within ongoing policy cycles.

Governance translation between levels

Across the five pilots, DRP functioned as a **governance translator**, structuring local experiences into micro-assessments and feeding them back into relevant policy arenas. In each pilot, governance arrangements determined the extent to which DRP could effectively translate between high-level policy frameworks and the everyday realities of rural life. In this way, DRP operationalised top-down policy objectives through place-based, actionable adjustments, drawing on locally grounded evidence and stakeholder engagement to both prevent negative impacts and enhance policy relevance and effectiveness for rural areas.

While the specific configurations of this translation process differed across policy domains and governance settings, several common patterns emerged. Some DRP pilots, such as [Garfagnana](#) and [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) (see all DRP pilot fiches in Annex 2), conducted micro DRP assessments of sectoral policy mixes concerning territorial disparities. Others looked at how national legal changes or support schemes were interpreted and implemented at different municipal or business contexts, as seen in [North Karelia](#) and [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#). A further group focused on mainstreamed strategies, such as the countywide digital inclusion strategy and action plan in [Gloucestershire](#). Across these cases, DRP consistently centred on embedding

locally grounded insights into the strategies, regulations and programmes shaping rural development.

The translational capacity of DRP depended on the extent to which insights generated through micro-assessments and feedback processes were reframed into policy-relevant formats, such as policy briefs, recommendations, workshop summaries or reflection notes, and on how well these outputs aligned with strategy, programme or legislative cycles. **When these conditions were met, DRP moved beyond a checklist exercise and functioned as a governance mechanism linking everyday realities with broader policy frameworks.** In practice, however, this translation proved highly uneven across the pilots. More effective vertical and horizontal integration of DRP results tended to occur in contexts characterised by intermediate institutions and well-established feedback mechanisms. By contrast, in more fragmented governance settings, DRP processes often remained confined to project level, reflecting the absence of clear institutional ownership for integrating results into formal decision-making.

Embedding DRP in live policy cycles

A key feature of DRP, as evidenced across the pilots, was its integration into live policy cycles rather than its use as an ex-post review of static policy documents. In each case, the DRP process (from defining the scope and guiding questions, through preparing evidence summaries and conducting micro-assessments to feeding back findings) was deliberately timed to intersect with consultations, programme periods or legislative rollouts, even if such alignment was only partially achieved.

In practice, this required aligning DRP activities with specific ‘windows of opportunity’, such as ongoing strategy consultations, early implementation phases of legislative reforms, or the preparation of new LEADER strategies and other programme documents. Accordingly, some pilots engaged with draft county-wide strategies, while others focused on regional forest programmes, integration reforms or emerging food policy mixes. Through this approach, DRP micro-assessments fed locally grounded insights directly into these ongoing policy processes, enabling timely and territorially sensitive input. Rather than retrospectively assessing finalised decisions, DRP contributed to shaping policy design and implementation as these processes unfolded.

The pilots further demonstrated how bottom-up micro-assessments could be effectively ‘stacked’, with the scoping, preparation, assessment and feedback phases of the DRP aligned with consultations, programme periods, and staged legislative rollouts. In this way, DRP became embedded within policy development processes rather than functioning as a peripheral checklist. From a governance perspective, this integration was important because **it allowed DRP to operate as an ongoing learning mechanism, enabling policy partners to adjust or reorient measures** while change was still possible, rather than relying on ex post compliance exercises.

At the same time, the pilots demonstrated that **such alignment was inherently fragile and dependent on available resources.** In some cases, capacity constraints and shifting policy timelines limited the extent to which DRP could be aligned with live policy processes. This raised broader questions about institutional readiness and the level of resourcing required for continuous decentralised proofing. From this perspective, decentralised rural proofing should be understood not merely as an evaluative tool, but as a governance mechanism. When embedded

in routine practices, it can improve policy coherence, support ongoing institutional learning, and strengthen territorial sensitivity by narrowing the gap between policy intentions and actual outcomes.

Anchor institutions and distributed roles

The pilots highlighted that **DRP does not operate as a free-floating toolkit, rather, it relies on anchor institutions embedded within rural governance ecosystems** that are able to carry out the **DRP steps in practice**. In each case, these anchor institutions took responsibility for defining the scope and objectives of **DRP**, convening key stakeholders, coordinating data collection for micro-assessments, and ensuring that findings are fed into formal policy processes. Across the five pilots, these anchoring functions were undertaken by a diverse set of intermediaries, such as Local Action Groups (LAGs) and regional associations, regional councils, universities, and specialised civil society or research organisations. Each brought a distinct combination of territorial knowledge, convening capacity, and access to policy networks, which shaped how effectively **DRP processes** were implemented within governance structures.

These arrangements confirmed that **DRP relied on trusted intermediaries capable of convening stakeholders**, managing data and navigating the ‘language’ of policy. For example, in [Nockregion-Oberkärnten](#), the regional association and LAG jointly anchored the **DRP process**, while in [Gloucestershire](#), libraries and voluntary sector organisations performed similar convening and translation roles within the digital inclusion agenda. In this way, **DRP translated locally grounded micro-assessments into narratives and recommendations that were legible within established decision-making structures**. From this perspective, scaling **DRP** is less a matter of creating new organisational layers and more about strengthening and mandating intermediary organisations with sufficient resources and authority to undertake and sustain repeated proofing cycles. At the same time, the pilots suggested that concentrating analytical and facilitative responsibilities within a limited number of intermediaries could create capacity bottlenecks under typical administrative conditions, potentially constraining both the scale and detail of **DRP implementation**.

Beyond simply channelling information upward, **DRP also revealed how responsibilities and capacities were distributed across governance levels and sectors in practice**. For instance, access to specific policy measures often depended on decisions taken at a higher level and on the capacity of local institutions to mobilise and support potential applicants. In this sense, **DRP plays an important diagnostic role**. It shows where governance systems help rural actors make use of available support, and where their ability to act is limited by gaps in coordination, resources or institutional capacity. Viewed this way, **DRP is a governance tool that makes it possible to surface and systematically analyse both the strengths and weaknesses of existing territorial governance configurations**.

Balancing distributional and procedural justice

Building on the previous sub-sections, which examined **DRP as a governance translator** and highlighted the roles of anchor institutions and intermediaries, this section demonstrates how the pilots operationalised two key dimensions of spatial justice, namely **distributional and procedural**.

Distributional spatial justice concerns the fairness of how resources, services and opportunities are distributed across territories and social groups. Procedural spatial justice, by contrast, relates to how power is distributed, who is able to participate, and how decisions are made. In this sense, DRP provides an analytical perspective for investigating questions such as ‘who gets what, where?’ and ‘who decides, and on what basis?’ (Madanipour et al. 2023).

On the distributional side, DRP micro assessments reflected how resources, services and opportunities actually flowed across rural territories and social groups. These observed patterns were then compared with identified needs, making it possible to reveal **mismatches that were often hidden in aggregated data**. This approach was applied across a range of policy areas in all pilot cases: from forest and territorial policy to business support schemes, CAP-related food measures, integration services, and digital infrastructure. For example, in [Garfagnana](#), DRP revealed that cohesion funds had systemically favoured urban and demographically stronger areas over more vulnerable rural municipalities. More broadly, this perspective makes it possible to uncover internal disparities and to better understand how different groups of actors are positioned within existing policy frameworks.

Procedurally, the DRP steps create concrete spaces for rural voices and deliberation, structured around guiding questions and evidence summaries. Through interviews, focus groups and workshops conducted during the pilots, the DRP methodology enabled rural actors to **reflect their lived experiences of policies**. For example, in [Gloucestershire](#), workshops brought together local authorities, health services and voluntary organisations to discuss digital inclusion in rural areas, challenge underlying assumptions, and examine patterns of inclusion or exclusion in policymaking processes. These steps go beyond symbolic consultation by explicitly asking whose voices are heard, who is absent, and how those absent perspectives might be better represented in the design and adjustment of policies.

Taken together, the distributional and procedural dimensions of spatial justice suggest that DRP does not aim to establish a single standard to determine whether policies affecting rural areas have ‘treated rural areas fairly’. Rather, it brings to light the differentiated impacts of policies within rural areas, highlighting both **winners and losers**, and questioning whether marginalised groups have meaningful opportunities to influence policies that affect them. For example, DRP can reveal situations in which more accessible or better-organised rural municipalities consistently capture a disproportionate share of funding, while more remote or capacity-constrained areas struggle to access the same support despite similar needs. At the same time, the pilots point to important limitations. Participation often remains modest and project-based, and there is no formal requirement for policymakers to act on the suggestions made. As a result, the effectiveness of DRP depends heavily on **political will**, administrative openness, and the broader institutional context in which decentralised rural proofing is embedded.

Key takeaways: Governance and institutional readiness

The preceding sub-sections show that DRP pilots did more than test a methodological approach; they highlighted concrete governance, capacity and spatial justice-related challenges that shape the feasibility of sustaining decentralised rural proofing over time. The following takeaways

summarise how this evidence points to areas where policy adaptation and institutional strengthening may be required.

- **Anchored governance mechanism:** DRP operates as a governance mechanism that links local micro-assessments to multilevel policy processes, bringing grounded rural experiences directly into decision-making.
- **Stress test for governance arrangements:** DRP functions as a stress test of multilevel governance, revealing whether existing arrangements can sustain continuous bottom-up feedback loops or leave results trapped at project level.
- **Policy-learning instead of checklist compliance:** When aligned with live policy cycles, DRP becomes a policy-learning mechanism that enables adjustment while windows of opportunity are open, rather than a post-hoc compliance exercise.
- **Critical role of intermediaries:** The impact of DRP depends on sufficiently mandated and resourced intermediary organisations that can convene actors, translate findings into policy language and channel them into formal arenas.
- **Diagnostic of territorial governance capacity:** DRP exposes where multilevel governance structures enable or constrain rural actors' ability to use available instruments, offering concrete evidence for institutional reform and capacity-building.
- **Spatial justice lens on distribution and procedure:** By surfacing both distributional and procedural tensions, DRP highlights where resource allocation and participation channels need to change if decentralised rural proofing is to be sustained over time.

3.4.3 Common analytical logic and strategic uses of DRP

This sub-section examines how the DRP pilots use decentralised rural proofing in practice: first as a tool for revealing intra-rural disparities, second as a method for improving mainstream policies, and finally as a basis for a transferable DRP model. Each perspective shows how the same DRP process can simultaneously illuminate distributional and procedural challenges within rural territories, inform the redesign of wider policy mixes, and highlight the evidence and data limitations that constrain the practice of continuous, territorially sensitive proofing.

DRP as a tool for revealing intra-rural disparities

One strategic use of DRP that emerges clearly from the pilots is its **role in uncovering intra-rural disparities**, i.e. differences within rural territories rather than only between rural and urban areas. Across the pilots, DRP micro-assessments highlight how access to measures, services, and opportunities varies between municipalities, sub-areas, and groups of actors. These variations are due to differences in institutional capacities, infrastructure, data practices, and levels of collective organisation. For example, the pilots revealed unequal municipal capacities to implement national legal reforms, structural divides between registered and unregistered producers within local food systems, and varying abilities among small rural businesses to access support and engage in regional development processes.

In summary, rural proofing is likely to be successful only insofar as it **identifies the 'rural' winners and losers, rather than treating 'the rural' as a single uniform category**. In this sense, its diagnostic role is strategically important. DRP, in particular, can provide policymakers with **nuanced evidence on where, to what extent, and how resources and interventions should be targeted**, thereby cautioning against one-size-fits-all policy approaches that risk reinforcing existing inequalities. However, the pilot studies also highlighted the limits of this approach. The translation of such evidence into policy is not always politically or instrumentally feasible, particularly within highly standardised funding frameworks that allow little or no room for territorial differentiation, even when there is clear evidence of intra-rural disparities.

DRP as a method for improving mainstream policy

A second key strategic use of DRP is its **application to mainstream policy areas where rural issues are often marginal**. Across the pilots, DRP was applied to general strategies and policy mixes to assess whether the rural dimension was adequately addressed, and whether issues such as territorial disparities and rural resources were integrated or treated as secondary concerns. In this sense, DRP helps ensure that rural perspectives are systematically considered, not only to prevent possible negative consequences for rural areas, but also to **improve the quality of the policy measure**. In some pilots, such as [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), DRP went further by identifying gaps within the existing policy framework. This included highlighting the absence of a local food policy and exploring the potential for a more territorially embedded policy framework for local food systems.

This strategic framing moves beyond the traditional, **defensive 'checklist' approach to rural proofing** and aligns with broader efforts to make mainstream policies more place sensitive. DRP should therefore be understood not as a one-off rural screening exercise, either before or after policy adoption, but as a tool for policy **design and refinement**. It can support targeting strategies, identifying continuing gaps in rural services, and mobilising local intermediaries and territorial assets. At the same time, the pilots highlighted practical constraints. In some cases, capacity constraints required DRP to be conducted retrospectively, limiting its ability to influence policy design in real time. Moreover, the uptake of its findings ultimately depended on political priorities and administrative decisions, as these had to be weighed against competing sectoral agendas and existing policy frameworks.

Cross-cutting strategic duality and implications for a DRP model

The pilots highlighted a clear **strategic duality of DRP**. It operates both as **a method for revealing intra-rural disparities and as a tool for improving mainstream policies** by integrating a rural perspective into their design and implementation. In practice, this means DRP can be used to trace how policies produce differentiated effects across rural territories and governance levels, to enhance the quality and relevance of broadly framed strategies and policy mixes, or to pursue both aims simultaneously within the same process.

This duality has important implications for how a DRP model is implemented in practice. Rather than adopting a ‘one-size-fits-all’ approach, each DRP application should clearly **define its primary strategic purpose at the outset** and align its guiding questions, data strategies and stakeholder configurations accordingly. From this perspective, success cannot be captured by a single indicator: DRP may generate value by uncovering hidden inequalities, informing policy reorientation, creating new spaces for rural voices, or testing institutional readiness for sustained proofing.

At the same time, the **shared analytical logic** across the pilots allowed for a degree of standardisation around key elements of the DRP approach. These included a core set of transferable questions addressing both access (distributional aspects) and voice (procedural aspects), an explicit attention to differences within rural areas, and systematic links to mainstream policy processes. The main challenge for future applications lies in maintaining this common foundation while preserving sufficient flexibility to adapt DRP to different strategic uses, sectors and governance contexts.

Evidence and data constraints in DRP micro-assessments

The pilots showed that the **evidence bases for DRP micro-assessments differed substantially** in scope, granularity and comparability. Some DRP exercises could draw on relatively well-developed statistical data and existing survey material, whereas others depended much more heavily on fragmented administrative sources, stakeholder knowledge and newly generated qualitative evidence. As a result, DRP does not operate on a basis of a single standardised dataset, but rather through context-specific combinations of evidence assembled around the policy issue at hand.

In [Garfagnana](#), for example, DRP combined two perspectives: stakeholders’ perceptions of how policy support was distributed across the territory, and an empirical analysis of actual funding allocations. This comparison revealed a severe mismatch between perceived and real patterns of territorial spending. The finding highlighted how limited transparency in the territorial distribution of resources could erode institutional trust and, over time, weaken the capacity of demographically declining areas to articulate their needs and compete effectively for resources.

The pilots also revealed **significant data gaps and limitations in data accessibility**, which constrained the scope and scale of DRP micro-assessments. In several cases, critical information on local actors, service use, or production capacities was either missing from official records, scattered across incomparable sources, or only available in highly aggregated form. This made it difficult to trace how policies were actually experienced and implemented in specific rural settings. As a result, teams often **relied on qualitative triangulation, proxy indicators and**

small-scale surveys to fill these gaps. While these approaches were effective in identifying governance-relevant blind spots, they provided only partial insight into the issues concerned. In [Gloucestershire](#), this challenge was particularly evident in the contrast between rich, hyper-local evidence gathered by community and third-sector organisations and the continued reliance on standardised quantitative indicators in formal monitoring systems. This mismatch led to underrepresentation of key aspects of rural digital exclusion and local support practices in official data.

As a result, many micro-assessments needed to be scaled down in scope or depth due to data access barriers, resource constraints, or tight implementation timelines. Compared to conventional, centrally conducted rural proofing, which typically relies on high-level, aggregated data, these DRP micro-assessments can nonetheless provide valuable insights into how policies are experienced in specific rural contexts. They help identify where particular territories or groups of actors are overlooked, even when the underlying data is partial and uneven. While such adaptive approaches, using proxies, triangulation, and qualitative inputs, can reveal important territorial blind spots, they cannot replace systematic, disaggregated information on rural territories and actors. This highlights a key limitation: **the feasibility and robustness of decentralised rural proofing depend not only on sound methods and participatory processes, but also on investment in data infrastructures** capable of supporting recurring, territorially sensitive assessments.

Key takeaways: analytical logic, strategic uses and data

A shared analytical logic, together with the strategic uses of DRP observed in the pilots, points to several areas where decentralised rural proofing could be strengthened, namely through clearer articulation of its purpose, stronger integration into mainstream policy processes, and more robust supporting data infrastructures.

- **Intra-rural differentiation lens:** DRP provides a systematic approach to uncover winners and losers within rural territories, challenging homogenised views of ‘the rural’ and supporting more finely targeted interventions.
- **Tool for improving mainstream policy:** Applying DRP to mainstream policy mixes shows how rural perspectives can be integrated into strategies where they are often marginal, thus improving overall policy effectiveness, not just mitigating negative impacts.
- **Strategic duality of DRP:** The pilots demonstrated a dual function of DRP, which could be used to analyse intra-rural disparities, improve mainstream policies, or combine both objectives within a single process.
- **Purpose-driven DRP design:** Effective DRP applications clearly define their primary strategic purpose from the outset and align guiding questions, data strategies and stakeholder configurations accordingly, rather than relying on a ‘one-size-fits-all’ model.
- **Multi-dimensional success criteria:** Assessing DRP requires multi-dimensional perspective, including revealing hidden inequalities, reorienting policy priorities,

opening spaces for rural voices and testing institutional readiness rather than relying on a single performance indicator.

- **Data-constrained but revealing diagnostics:** Even when based on partial and uneven data, DRP micro-assessments, through transparent triangulation, can uncover governance-relevant blind spots, while at the same time highlighting the need for investment in territorially disaggregated data infrastructures.

4. From rural evidence to place-based policy learning

The RUSTIK Living Labs showed that evidence-based rural policymaking is not simply about producing better data. Across the Pilot Regions, data experiments generated new insights into territorial disparities, sectoral interdependencies, under-recognised actors and governance gaps. However, the policy relevance of this evidence depends on whether and how the governance systems can make use of it. In this sense, evidence-based policymaking is closely tied to the capacity to translate evidence into action.

The previous sections of this report demonstrate this across different steps of the process. The Transition Narratives showed that Living Labs operated within highly diverse institutional and policy settings. Some Pilot Regions benefitted from more coherent multi-level policy frameworks, stronger cooperative networks and supportive institutional facilitators. Others operated in more fragmented governance contexts, with weaker coordination or and less room for local policy action

- The Theory of Change models translated these different contextual differences into intervention logics. They highlighted the conditions under which evidence could be taken up in practice, including institutional receptivity, stakeholder engagement, intermediary capacity and sustained political attention.
- The policy impact pathways then showed how experimental evidence could support policy learning through three main routes: cross-sectoral integration, territorially sensitive allocation and governance adaptation.
- Finally, the Decentralised Rural Proofing pilots tested whether local evidence and stakeholder knowledge could be embedded more systematically into ongoing policy processes.

Taken together, these findings suggest that the main question is not whether rural territories can generate useful evidence. They can. The more difficult question is to understand the conditions under which this evidence is turned into policy learning.

4.1 Governance conditions enabling policy uptake of evidence and data tools

The uptake of evidence and data tools into policy takes place within complex governance arrangements. Evidence and analytical tools may be developed to inform different levels of government, policy instruments, and stages of the policy process, and may serve a range of functions, from addressing immediate needs to raising new issues and opportunities on the policy agenda.

Drawing on the experience of the RUSTIK Living Lab data experiments, which aimed to improve policy responses to rural transitions, **three governance enabling conditions appear particularly important** for the recognition and integration of evidence and data tools into policy:

1. a clear institutional entry point and/or ongoing/anticipated policy process,
2. a strategic intermediary organisation working at a functional territorial scale, and
3. sustained resources and analytical capacity.

First, evidence is more likely to influence policy in the short-term when it is connected to a clear institutional entry point and when evidence generation coincides with an ongoing or anticipated planning, monitoring or reform process. In some Pilot Regions, the Living Lab experiments were linked from the outset to existing strategies, laws or programmes.

For example, [Monmouthshire](#) connected its work on young people's lived experiences to the assessment logic of the Well-being of Future Generations Act. [North Karelia](#) developed service assessment and monitoring tool on immigrant integration at a time when municipalities were taking on new responsibilities under the national Integration Act reform. [Galicia](#) linked its decision-support system tool to the regional Model Settlements instrument, while [Gloucestershire](#) connected local digital inclusion evidence to service commissioning and digital inclusion strategies. In these cases, evidence had a potential route into decision-making because there was an existing institutional process through which findings and tools could be interpreted and used.

This alignment with a policy process is most effective when relevant public institutions are actively involved in shaping both the generation of evidence and the development of data tools. Their participation helps ensure that the questions addressed, the parameters selected, or the intended audience respond to concrete policy needs. This strengthens policy ownership of the resulting evidence/tool and increases the likelihood of their uptake. More broadly, the RUSTIK experience suggests that public institutions are more likely to support the development and use of evidence and data tools when they see clear practical value. This may include improving decision-making, strengthening the legitimacy of choices, or enhancing the efficiency of resource allocation. For example, in resource-constrained administrations facing high application volumes, tools such as decision-support systems (e.g. as illustrated by the [Galician](#) case) can add value. They can improve the efficiency, consistency, and transparency of project selection processes, while also helping to prioritise the most vulnerable territories. Their uptake appears more likely when public bodies perceive clear benefits in terms of both legitimacy and efficiency.

At the same time, the RUSTIK experience suggests that when evidence generation is not clearly connected to an ongoing policy process or a recognised policy need, the role of evidence and data

tools shifts more towards agenda-setting and advocacy. In such cases, data experiments tend to be more exploratory in nature, focusing on understanding the different interests, actors, and forms of value associated with a territorial asset. As a result, their contribution to policy is less immediate and more oriented towards long-term learning. This includes building recognition of under-represented actors, revealing previously overlooked interdependencies, and strengthening the knowledge base and organisational capacities needed for future action. This appears particularly relevant in governance contexts where responsibilities are fragmented, coordination mechanisms are weak, or multi-level arrangements are misaligned due to institutional or political challenges. In such contexts, evidence and data tools can help create policy readiness by preparing insights and capacities that can be mobilised when future policy opportunities emerge.

Second, the uptake of evidence depends strongly on intermediary organisations and coordination capacity. The Transition Narratives highlighted the importance of cooperative networks and institutional facilitators, including LAGs, regional associations, councils, universities and development agencies. These actors played a critical translation role. They connected local stakeholders to higher-level policy processes, interpreted evidence in policy-relevant ways and sustained dialogue beyond the life span of individual projects.

The [Nockregion](#) provided a clear example. Evidence on small rural businesses helped make a dispersed and previously under-recognised group more visible within regional development processes. However, the policy relevance of this evidence depended on the capacity of the LAG and the regional association to bring municipalities, businesses and other actors together around a shared development agenda. Similarly, in [North Karelia](#), the institutionalisation of the immigrant integration survey by the Regional Council increased the likelihood that the tool would continue to inform local decision-making beyond the project. By contrast, in more fragmented contexts, such as [Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#) or [Zaječar](#), the absence of or limited capacity within such intermediary organisations constrained the translation of evidence on local food systems into coordinated territorial action.

Third, evidence-based policymaking requires flexible instruments and sufficient local analytical capacity. Several experiments showed that granular data could reveal needs that standardised policy instruments were not well equipped to address. For example, in [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#), the Quality-of-Life Index showed intra-municipal disparities that were relevant for urban planning and renewal. In [Gloucestershire](#), the digital inclusion dashboard pointed to spatial gaps in service provision and the need for better data integration across service providers. In [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#), water vulnerability mapping revealed differentiated territorial needs that did not fit neatly within existing funding categories. These examples show that evidence can improve territorial targeting, but only if funding rules, eligibility criteria and planning instruments are flexible enough to support differentiated responses.

At the same time, the use of sophisticated data tools requires adequate capacity. Rural municipalities and intermediary organisations may lack the staff, skills or resources needed to maintain dashboards, interpret indicators, or integrate qualitative evidence into planning processes. This points to a broader lesson: data tools alone are not sufficient. They need to be accompanied by capacity-building, sustained funding for data infrastructure, and institutional routines that embed the use of evidence into everyday decision-making.

4.2 Matching governance arrangements and intervention logics

The comparison across Pilot Regions suggests that no single governance model ensures the uptake of evidence in policymaking. Decentralised systems may create more space for place-based action, but this depends on whether local actors have sufficient capacity, mandate and resources to act. Conversely, more centralised systems may provide greater strategic consistency, yet they risk overlooking territorial diversity, particularly where mechanisms for incorporating bottom-up feedback are limited. The key determinant is therefore not the governance model itself, but the degree of alignment between the governance arrangement, the intervention logic and the policy pathway through which evidence is expected to inform decisions. This alignment helps explain why similar types of evidence generate different policy implications across the Living Labs.

Drawing on the findings presented throughout D4.3, particularly the Transition Narratives, Theory of Change models, policy impact pathways and Decentralised Rural Proofing pilots, Table 9 distils the key patterns observed across the Living Labs. It outlines recurring governance settings and links them to the main opportunities, risks and intervention logics through which rural evidence can support policy learning and adaptation.

Table 9: Governance setting, opportunities, risks and intervention logics for evidence uptake in rural policy learning

Governance setting	Main opportunities	Main risks	Possible intervention logic
Coherent multi-level governance with policy anchors	Mechanisms to support dialogue and integration of evidence into existing strategies, reforms, or assessment cycles	Uptake of evidence depends on factors, e.g. available resources	Use evidence for policy refinement and territorial targeting
Decentralised but fragmented governance	Local experimentation and stakeholder mobilisation are possible	Weak coordination and limited scaling	Use evidence to strengthen networks, intermediaries and collective organisation
Centralised or top-down governance	Strategic frameworks and national instruments can provide direction	Local evidence has limited influence over rules and resources	Use evidence for advocacy, regulatory feedback, and policy adjustment
Intermediary-led governance	Coordination can operate at the scale of territorial assets or shared systems (e.g. food value chains, labour markets, service networks)	Depends on intermediary capacity and resources	Use evidence to support cross-sectoral integration, territorial branding, and shared resource governance

The patterns summarised in the table were visible across the Living Lab cases and help explain why different types of evidence pointed towards different forms of policy learning and adaptation. For example, evidence on territorial assets supported cross-sectoral policy arguments in [Trojan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin](#), [Zaječar](#), [Mazowieckie](#) and [Świętokrzyskie](#) by showing that activities such as local food production, tourism, culture, crafts and the use of natural resources were not isolated sectors, but part of wider territorial value systems. However, translating this evidence into action depended on governance arrangements that can effectively coordinate across policy measures, linking agriculture, tourism, skills, infrastructure, as well as branding and funding measures.

Similarly, evidence on territorial disparities supported allocation arguments in [Monmouthshire](#), [Sant Miquel de Balenyà](#), [Gloucestershire](#) and [Parma-Piacenza-Ferrara](#). However, such evidence only became actionable only where policy frameworks allowed sufficient flexibility to prioritise specific places, groups or types of intervention. Finally, evidence on under-recognised actors and coordination gaps supported governance arguments in [Nockregion](#), [North Karelia](#), [Galicia](#), [Rhein-Hunsrück](#) and other regions. In these cases, the main policy implication was not limited to adjusting funding measures, but extended to strengthening participation, coordination and institutional learning.

4.3 Promising design principles for evidence- and place-based policy development

The report points to a set of design features for policies that seek to make more effective use of evidence to respond to rural needs and transitions.

1. **Create clear routes for local evidence to enter decision-making**, for example through decentralised multiannual assessment cycles, participatory strategy revisions or programme design;
2. **Combine quantitative, qualitative and experiential evidence as part of the above**, recognising that lived experience and local knowledge are central to understanding and responding to rural transitions.
3. **Allow territorial differentiation in resource allocation**, enabling funding to be tailored to differing rural needs rather than allocated solely through uniform eligibility rules;
4. **Support cross-sectoral policy mixes** that recognise the multiple forms of value associated with rural assets (e.g. food; forests; water; skills) and mobile coordinated action across sectors such as agriculture, tourism, culture, environment, wellbeing and infrastructure;
5. **Mandate and resource intermediaries**, such as LAGs, regional associations, councils or civil society organisations, to convene diverse actors and transform local knowledge into shared strategic directions and concrete proposals;
6. **Incentivise collective action through funding models**, moving beyond support to individual beneficiaries to promote cooperative and system-level solutions.

From this perspective, LEADER/CLLD, regional development strategies, local development plans, service-delivery monitoring tools, digital inclusion strategies and territorial land or water management instruments can all support evidence-based rural policy. Their effectiveness depends on how they are governed, funded and connected to local evidence.

4.4 Added value of Decentralised Rural Proofing

As the preceding sections have shown, the effectiveness of rural evidence depends on clear policy anchors, intermediary organisations, flexible instruments and sufficient analytical capacity. Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) provides a practical way to strengthen the link between rural evidence and policy learning. Its added value lies in bringing rural proofing closer to the territories, actors and governance arrangements affected by policy. Rather than functioning as a centralised process, DRP operates as a micro-assessment, and examines how specific policies work in particular rural contexts, who benefits, who may be excluded, and whether local actors have meaningful opportunities to influence policy design and implementation. In this sense, DRP complements existing, more centralised rural proofing arrangements by providing concrete, place-based insights that can inform the fine-tuning of strategies, programmes and legal reforms.

The DRP pilots demonstrated three main contributions of this approach. First, the DRP revealed intra-rural disparities that were often hidden in aggregated data. Second, it enhanced mainstream policies by integrating rural evidence into strategies or reforms where rural concerns might otherwise remain marginal, thereby strengthening their overall relevance and effectiveness. Third, DRP functioned as a governance 'stress test', showing whether existing institutions were capable of sustaining bottom-up feedback loops or whether evidence remained confined to the project level. These contributions are particularly relevant in policy areas where rural perspectives are not explicitly prioritised, but where territorially differentiated impacts are likely, such as digital inclusion, integration policies or thematic cohesion instruments.

At the same time, these benefits do not materialise automatically and depend on specific enabling conditions. This is particularly important when considering the transferability of the DRP approach. DRP requires an anchor institution, access to relevant evidence, stakeholder trust, sufficient capacity to conduct micro-assessments and a policy process that is open to feedback. Its feasibility therefore depends on the same governance conditions identified throughout this report: intermediaries, policy anchors, flexible instruments and institutional capacity. These factors should be assessed before implementing DRP in new contexts. Where these conditions are only partially in place, DRP can still be used in a more exploratory mode to map governance blind spots and information gaps. However, expectations regarding its immediate policy impact should remain modest.

Overall, the DRP pilots suggested that DRP was most effective when it was embedded within an iterative governance process. It generates the greatest value when micro-assessments are co-designed with local actors, interpreted through place-based intervention logics, and connected to policy cycles that allow for adjustment of strategies, programmes or legal reforms. Under these conditions, Living Labs and DRP can work in tandem by turning rural evidence into concrete signals for policy adaptation. This approach helps move rural policy beyond generic territorial categories towards more responsive, fair and context-sensitive forms of rural development.

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6. Annexes

Annex 1: Decentralised Rural Proofing – overall approach

6.1 Background

According to the RUSTIK DoA, Task 4.3 (c) is dedicated to ‘Support to LL stakeholders in co-creating and improving methods for distributed rural proofing and policy impact assessment on the basis of a better understanding of rural transition and functional rural areas, incorporating the novel indicator arrays. In this task the benefits of the ToC approach will be extended to procedures for proofing and evaluation of existing or proposed policies.’

Refining the initial terminology to better reflect the actual purpose and nature of the type of process, we arrived at the term ‘**decentralised rural proofing**’ (DRP), which is being used in the document at hand.

At present, formal rural proofing practices are limited in Europe. Where they do exist – such as in Finland and the UK – experience shows that rural proofing tends to follow predominantly top-down approaches, in which assessments are mainly led by central-level authorities with limited involvement of local-level, rural stakeholders. Where there is local-level involvement, it is voluntary, and very much dependent on the awareness, resources, and capacity of the entities. Moreover, the rural proofing approaches typically focus on identifying potential negative impacts on rural areas – rather than exploring how rural assets and opportunities could actively inform and shape the policy.

6.2 Testing decentralised rural proofing in RUSTIK Living Labs

Objectives of the testing

The objective of this task is to explore whether – and how – a decentralised model of rural proofing (DRP) can function effectively. A distinctive characteristic of such a model is the distribution of roles and responsibilities across different levels and actors. Rather than relying on a central-level authority to lead the rural proofing process, this approach mobilises rural stakeholders – such as civil society, local authorities and community organisations – to participate in assessing or monitoring the rural implications of policies and programmes within their own context. This shift opens the door not only to identifying how policies address specific rural needs, but also to recognising and leveraging rural opportunities as part of the policy design.

In practice, the idea of decentralised rural proofing is to test how rural proofing can be carried out bottom-up, using local data and involving local stakeholders and networks. Given the limitations of the RUSTIK project, the aim is not to conduct a comprehensive rural impact study. Instead, the idea is to identify some approach to rural proofing at the local level and, within this, facilitate collaborative, place-based micro-assessment(s) which involve multiple rural partners and focus

on understanding how the selected policies relate to local needs and opportunities within the concerned territory.

At the EU level, this testing contributes to ongoing efforts under the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas to make rural proofing more operational and place-sensitive and offers practical insights into how local actors and instruments (such as LAGs) can support policy learning across levels.

Living Labs as testing grounds

Targeted, small-scale tests of the feasibility and practical value of decentralised rural proofing – i.e. to explore how local actors can reflect on the rural relevance of specific policies using locally available data and insights – will be carried out in the following Living Labs:

- Garfagnana, Italy
- Gloucestershire, UK
- Nockregion-Oberkärnten, Austria
- North Karelia, Finland
- Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin, Bulgaria

The selection was guided by the objective to cover the range of pathways identified in WP4:

- **Pathway 1 – Inter-sectoral policy integration:** This pathway focuses on how experiment insights and tools can be used to highlight the need for integration of multiple sectoral actions in response to complex rural challenges. It invites partners to reflect on how combining efforts across thematic sectors – rather than relying on separate, sector-specific interventions – can lead to more coherent and effective policy responses.
- **Pathway 2 – Territoriality and resource allocation:** This pathway delves into territoriality – the territorial rationale of policies, including the targeting of appropriate spatial or functional scales and addressing gaps in resource allocation. It aims to use insights and evidence about the importance of clearly defining a territorial focus of policies, where this focus is informed by functional dynamics, territorial imbalances or spatial interdependences rather than administrative boundaries alone.
- **Pathway 3 – Governance and collaboration:** This pathway focuses on how to use insights and tools from the experiments to improve governance and collaboration. It supports reflection on how rural transitions can be better enabled through more effective multi-level governance (MLG) and participatory decision-making.

The identification of pathway(s) relevance for each Living Lab was not predefined but emerged through individual bilateral meetings with the Pilot Regions. During these meetings, the WP4 team worked with each Pilot Region to determine which transition logic best corresponded to their local challenges, institutional structures, and policy focus. This participatory matching ensured that the decentralised rural proofing test reflects both local realities and WP4's analytical framework.

Approach and process

The testing in each of the Living Labs named above will follow an overall common approach and procedure, which is finetuned and adapted to fit each individual case.

In line with this, **specific objectives** and **policy focus** will be defined for each of the LLs.

The **specific actors to be involved** in each DRP test at LL level will be identified, such as the overall DRP process lead, local facilitators and data contributors, as well as actors to be involved in assessment and validation steps.

The testing process will entail the following proposed steps and timeline:

- **Step 1 – Framing and Guiding Questions (September 2025):** Translation of criteria/emerging challenges into a set of guiding questions.
- **Step 2 – Data synthesis (late September to early October 2025):** Compilation of relevant data on specific needs and policies/programmes involved to feed into a brief evidence summary to be used in assessment.
- **Step 3 – Micro-assessment (October to November 2025):** Use the guiding questions and evidence summary to review the selected policies, their coherence with needs, governance failures and interactions with other policies at the different levels. Methods may include e.g. short interviews, semi-structured questionnaires or feedback forms, and desk research.
- **Step 4 – Feedback and policy reflection (late November 2025):** Share initial DRP insights with local/regional stakeholders to reflect jointly on gaps and alignment opportunities (e.g. through a roundtable) and propose consequently needed adjustments.
- **Step 5 – Reporting and contribution to WP4 (December 2025):** Preparation of a short DRP testing report to feed into WP4s Deliverable 4.3 and cross-regional synthesis, including:
 - Scope, method, and actors involved
 - Key findings and policy alignment observations
 - Reflections on the role of DRP enabler
 - Comments on feasibility, transferability, and learning

Annex 2: DRP Fiches

6.3 DRP Fiche – Garfagnana

Regional context and transition challenge

Garfagnana is a predominantly mountainous rural area in north-western Tuscany, characterised by diverse but often remote landscapes, extensive forest coverage, and small, dispersed municipalities. The key challenges are long-term population decline, low population density, and pronounced demographic ageing.

The two closely linked transition challenges are: 1) strengthening the multifunctional role of forestry as part of the climate and environmental transition, and 2) supporting community regeneration in the face of demographic decline in mountain areas.

Policy focus

The DRP focused on three complementary dimensions: 1) analysis of existing policies, 2) identification of unmet needs, and 3) evaluation of territorial coherence.

First, it reviewed recent measures (including CAP forestry support measures, regional legislation supporting forest management and producer associations, and EU/national funding) to identify achievements and shortcomings, such as incomplete forest management planning and the limited scale of local processing capacity.

Second, it analysed past and planned expenditures, access rules, uptake, and effectiveness of implemented measures.

Third, it evaluated the coherence between policy instruments and the area's evolving challenges, particularly demographic decline and structural fragilities, as well as opportunities linked to forest-based development, with a view to defining a more coherent and context-appropriate policy mix through multi-level governance and the active involvement of local actors.

Rationale, objectives and scope

The objective of the DRP pilot was to assess how effectively current and future policy mixes respond to the specific needs of the territory, with particular attention to the forestry system and related socio-economic activities.

In addition to assessing the specific policies, the pilot aimed to test the added value of DRP as both a methodological approach and governance innovation.

To this end, the assessment was guided by a set of questions:

- Is the Pilot Region able to access the specific policy instruments under examination?
- Does the policy framework adequately support the needs, weaknesses, and strengths of the Pilot Region?

- Does the existing policy delivery system facilitate or hinder access to policy instruments at the local level?
- Is the policy under examination complementary to, or in tension with, other policy initiatives addressing ongoing transitions?
- Does the policy take into account internal territorial disparities within the Pilot Region, including differences between areas and social groups with uneven levels of well-being and resource endowments?

Actors and methods

The DRP process was led by the Institute for Rural Development Research (Crea), Italy.

The DRP process consisted of six steps, which aimed to combine territorial evidence, policy analysis and multi-level stakeholder engagement:

Table 10 Garfagnana DRP process

Steps	Involved stakeholders
1) Analysis of unmet needs in the Pilot Region	Unions of mountain municipalities, representatives of different actors within the forest supply chain, members of the LAG board
2) Review of ongoing and future policies for 2023–2027	LAG technical structure
3) Integration of evidence-based material on past/most recent forest policies 2014–2020 (including their uptake/impact)	Same as in Step 1
4) Focus group consultations with different stakeholders	Representatives of regional forestry department, LAG, unions of mountain municipalities, NGO.
5) Drafting of a short policy review document	LAG technical structure; Same as in Steps 1 and 3 for feedback
6) Discussion with regional authorities based on the short policy review document	Regional authorities

Key findings

The DRP process of Garfagnana demonstrates the added value of combining an evidence-based review of past policies with structured stakeholder engagement and direct dialogue with the

regional administration, creating a direct feedback loop between policy design, delivery and territorial experience.

The DRP process performed a set of interrelated functions that clarify its analytical and operational contribution:

First, DRP played a crucial **awareness-raising role**. By providing stakeholders with systematic, evidence-based information on policy allocations, delivery mechanisms, and outcomes, it helped overcome fragmented or perception-driven understandings of public intervention. This is particularly important in rural contexts, where information asymmetries and limited transparency often constrain meaningful engagement. In this sense, DRP acts as a cognitive tool that aligns local perceptions with empirical evidence, supporting informed participation in place-based policymaking.

Second, the process strengthened **policy assessment** by complementing formal evaluation frameworks with territorially grounded insights. It helped identify effects and implementation issues that had remained underexplored in previous assessments.

Third, DRP **enhanced local advocacy capacity**. Through structured dialogue, stakeholders were better able to formulate needs and proposals in a way that was consistent with existing policy frameworks and governance constraints. Importantly, this shifted focus from demands for additional resources towards improvements in governance arrangements, coordination mechanisms, and policy delivery processes.

Fourth, the process **strengthened the capacity of regional administrations to respond to rural needs**. By providing structured feedback on the territorial distribution of funding, the effectiveness of delivery mechanisms, and the barriers faced by local actors, DRP operated as an interface between rural territories and the regional decision-making system. This feedback loop reduced information asymmetries and supported a more differentiated understanding of rural areas as diverse systems with distinct governance and capacity constraints.

Finally, DRP **reinforced multi-level governance by enabling** a two-way flow of information between local and regional levels and improving coordination across policy sectors and governance scales. Rather than adding an additional layer of consultation, DRP operated as a connective mechanism, aligning local knowledge with regional strategic priorities.

Overall, the Garfagnana experience shows that DRP should be understood not simply as an evaluative tool, but as a governance mechanism capable of enhancing policy coherence, institutional learning, and territorial sensitivity. By embedding rural proofing with ongoing governance practices, it helps bridge the gap between policy intentions and outcomes.

6.4 DRP Fiche - Gloucestershire

Regional context and transition challenge

Gloucestershire is a predominantly rural county, characterised by a network of market towns that act as key employment and service hubs alongside two main urban centres, Gloucester and Cheltenham.

The main transition challenge identified for RUSTIK related to digital transition, particularly addressing the persistent rural–urban digital divide. Gaps in high-speed connectivity, digital skills, and access to digital services constrain rural businesses, limit access to services, and increase the risk of social exclusion. While initiatives to improve digital inclusion are underway, evidence on their longer-term impacts remains limited. More granular rural data and more understanding of rural-urban interdependencies and synergies are needed to better understand the local effects of digital exclusion and to inform more targeted and effective policy interventions.

Policy focus

The DRP pilot focused primarily on the **Digital Infrastructure, Inclusion and Innovation Strategy (DIIS)** developed by Gloucestershire County Council (GCC). This strategy ties directly with the RUSTIK Living Lab data experiment in Gloucestershire, which aimed to generate bottom-up digital inclusion data, particularly through Gloucestershire Rural Community Council (GRCC) and its network, and to better integrate rural insights into service delivery and digital access planning. DIIS offered strong potential for DRP as it was still under development, and it directly affects rural residents' access to services, learning, health, and participation.

In addition, two other related strategies were reviewed as part of the DRP exercise, namely: the **UK Digital Inclusion Action Plan (2025)**, and the **Plan for Digital Health and Care** in Gloucestershire.

Rationale, objectives and scope

The DRP was initiated when GCC invited the Countryside and Community Research Institute (CCRI) to support the development of a new digital infrastructure, inclusion and innovation strategy, the DIIS. CCRI joined the Digital Inclusion Strategy Advisory Group (DISAG), and GCC and CCRI agreed a joint research programme to strengthen rural social inclusion within the strategy.

The DRP focused on three objectives: 1) assessing how rural contexts were reflected in the strategy, 2) identifying potential rural impacts, and 3) informing the forthcoming Action Plan. While CCRI's DRP efforts were centred on digital inclusion, it also considered links to digital infrastructure and innovation.

Although originally intended to align with the strategy consultation phase, timing constraints meant the DRP ultimately informed the Action Plan rather than the draft strategy, making it effectively an ex post rural proofing exercise.

Actors and methods

Due to the short timeframe, the DRP relied on a small core group of stakeholders, with CCRI leading the process, GCC acting as the policy partner, and DISAG members supporting data collection and workshop engagement.

The approach taken in the DRP covered the following phases, outlined in Table 11.

Table 11: Gloucestershire DRP activities

Method	Activity (led by)	Target group	Objective
Online survey (n=24)	Co-developing online survey questions (CCRI/GCC)	Organisations providing digital inclusion support in Gloucestershire.	To gain an overview of up-to-date support provision, beneficiary groups, and geographic gaps.
	Online survey (CCRI)		
	Analysis using JISC (CCRI)		
	Analysis using smart dashboard (CCRI)		
Workshop (n=13)	In-person workshop (CCRI)	Stakeholders were engaged through the same networks used for the survey, complemented by targeted invitations to participants from previous RUSTIK LL activities.	To review the rural implications of the digital strategy using the 7-step framework ² developed by the New Zealand Ministry of Primary Industries.
Expert engagement (n=4 interviews & 2 x workshop participation)	Supplementary qualitative interviews & participation in external workshops (CCRI)	Interviews were held with a rural poverty/policy consultant, members of a rural digital inclusion project, a local health service official involved in social prescribing, and representatives from a digital support NGO.	Interviews complemented other data sources by filling key gaps; they were loosely structured but guided by NZ rural proofing stages to prompt open discussion on rural digital challenges and opportunities.
Policy review	Rapid review of the UK Digital Inclusion Action Plan & the Gloucestershire Digital Health and Care Plan (CCRI)		

The DRP report was shared with stakeholders and GCC to help inform and shape the forthcoming Action Plan through its recommendations.

Key findings

Key insights concerning the strategy

The DIIS strategy acknowledges key digital challenges affecting rural areas, such as connectivity gaps, exclusion, and the need for place-based innovation, and identifies delivery mechanisms

² <https://www.mpi.govt.nz/resources-and-forms/registers-and-lists/rural-proofing-guidance-forpolicymakers>

including libraries and voluntary organisations, and proposes a website and public campaigns to promote digital support services.

However, the strategy largely adopts a ‘digital by default’ approach and lacks a targeted approach for rural communities and those unable to engage digitally. The DRP added value by introducing a rural lens, enabling stakeholders to highlight delivery challenges and propose practical inputs for the forthcoming Action Plan.

Critical gaps

Two key gaps constrain effective rural digital inclusion: 1) weak coordination across providers delivering infrastructure, skills, and innovation support; and 2) lack of granular local data, limiting understanding of rural needs and the design of targeted interventions

Opportunities for alignment

There is strong potential to improve alignment by: strengthening coordination between providers; linking digital inclusion more clearly with related sectors (e.g. health, housing, skills); adopting place-based delivery approaches; and improving monitoring and feedback mechanisms. These opportunities are currently limited by data gaps and the absence of a systematic rural focus in the DIIS strategy.

Resource allocation considerations

Rural digital inclusion efforts appear comparatively under-resourced, although significant urban challenges also persist (e.g. in Gloucester city). This calls for a balanced but explicit recognition of rural needs. Stakeholders emphasised the importance of reflecting higher rural delivery costs, particularly in procurement, and ensuring rural areas are clearly addressed in the Action Plan. However, its absence makes it too early to assess future allocation outcomes.

Implications for future

The DRP pilot confirmed that DRP is feasible and valuable, particularly for strengthening stakeholder engagement and ensuring that rural considerations are integrated into county-level strategies. Its effectiveness depends on:

- Early integration in the policy cycle to shape strategies before finalisation.
- Meaningful engagement with rural stakeholders.

Formalising rural proofing would enhance its impact, but this requires more time, resources and political will. The pilot should be seen as an indicative model rather than a fully scalable approach without additional investment.

6.5 DRP Fiche – Nockregion- Oberkärnten

Regional context and transition challenge

The **Nockregion-Oberkärnten** is a rural area in Austria characterized by significant socio-economic challenges due to unfavourable demographic dynamics. The region faces negative birth and migration rates, resulting in a shrinking and aging population with a diminishing number of young and employable adults. This has created a critical scarcity of skilled workers across all sectors, particularly in tourism.

The main transition challenge relates to the socio-economic and demographic transition, specifically the region's strategic objective of "becoming the best working and living region". **Small Rural Businesses (SRBs)**—defined here as those with fewer than 50 employees—are the backbone of the regional economy, with firms of fewer than 10 employees making up 94% of all businesses in Carinthia. These SRBs are vital for maintaining service diversity in remote municipalities and combating village centre vacancies, yet they are often "invisible" in strategic policy frameworks.

Policy focus

The DRP pilot focused on three key policies and initiatives relevant to regional strategy and planning processes for SRBs:

1. **The LEADER Local Development Strategy (2023-2027):** Focused on action fields like increasing regional value, sustainable resource development, and public welfare.
2. **The “Best Living and Working Region” Flagship Initiative:** A regional program anchored in the LEADER strategy aimed at site development for affordable living, mobility, and quality workplaces.
3. **The Carinthian Economic Development Funds (KWF):** A provincial agency responsible for European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), Just Transition Fund, and Interreg funds, providing business support, consulting, and innovation subsidies.

The pilot also utilized a comparison with the **Tyrolean IBW/ERDF model**, which employs a more decentralized, bottom-up governance approach via Local Action Groups (LAGs) compared to the centralized Carinthian model.

Rationale, objectives and scope

The DRP aimed to test the feasibility of a decentralized model using LAGs as intermediaries to make SRBs more visible in rural policy frameworks. Specific objectives included assessing how regional strategies reflect rural needs, exploring the equality and coherence of specific policies, and determining if bottom-up reflections by local actors can improve spatial targeting in existing planning. The scope was intentionally narrow, focusing on a qualitative identification of the DRP approach rather than a comprehensive impact study.

Actors and methods

The process was coordinated by the **Federal Institute of Agricultural Economics, Rural and Mountain Research (BAB)** in collaboration with the **Regional Association Nockregion (RVN)** and the **LAG Nockregion-Oberkärnten**.

The qualitative approach involved five main stages:

1. **Framing:** Clarification of guiding questions with the WP4 team and local partners.
2. **Data Collection:** Gathering written information and conducting personal interviews (telephone/online).
3. **Synthesis:** Information analysis and conclusion drafting by BAB.
4. **Feedback:** Policy reflection and discussion of conclusions with local stakeholders.
5. **Reporting:** Finalizing the DRP findings.

Table 12: Nockregion-Oberkärnten DRP Information Pillars

Pillar	Method	Participants
Policy-responsible Institutions	2 Questionnaires, 3 Interviews	Representatives of LAG/RVN, KWF, and Tyrolean managers.
SRBs and representatives	3 questionnaires	SRB owners and representatives affected by the policies.
External Assessment	1 Questionnaire	BAB (external party)

Key findings

Key insights concerning the policies

- **Relevance:** Regional policies generally recognize SRBs as the backbone of development, focusing on "value creation," location brand positioning, and innovation.
- **Accessibility:** SRBs can submit LEADER projects, but they are not the main target group; the primary focus is often on overarching framework conditions rather than individual businesses.
- **Barriers to Engagement:** While SRBs are represented in decision-making bodies, they often face significant constraints in time and financial resources, making active participation difficult even when interested.

Critical gaps

- **Information Overload:** There is an impression of "parallel activities" from different institutions and a "flood of information," suggesting a need for a more streamlined, "one-stop-shop" approach for information flow.

- **Data Challenges:** While business data is accessible, **data protection laws** often hinder its utilization for spatial mapping or targeted measures. Furthermore, maintaining up-to-date regional data is costly and requires specialized skills.

Governance and Alignment

- **Centralization vs. Decentralization:** The Carinthian centralized funding model (KWF) ensures efficiency but offers limited opportunities for rural regions to shape priorities compared to the Tyrolean decentralized model.
- **Synergy Opportunities:** Integrating ERDF and European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (LEADER) funds at the regional level—such as through a Community-Led Local Development (CLLD) approach—could create stronger local ownership and higher project quality.

Implications for future

The pilot confirmed that **DRP is a valuable complement** to conventional evaluations. Future applications should consider the following:

- **Quantitative Integration:** Future DRP should move beyond purely qualitative approaches to include quantitative data and specific rural indicators (e.g., business data differentiated by sector, size, and gender).
- **Budget and Time:** Dedicated budget and time must be allocated specifically for rural proofing activities.
- **Vision-Driven Planning:** Following a common regional vision (like "Best Living and Working Region") is essential; when infrastructure and services are offered, demand and development often follow.
- **Legal Clarity:** Municipalities and regional associations should be granted clearer rights to process non-sensitive company data under GDPR to implement data-based development measures.

6.6 DRP Fiche – North Karelia

Regional context and transition challenge

North Karelia is a region facing ongoing population decline and rapid ageing, driven by a significant natural decrease. Although positive net migration, particularly international immigration, partly offsets this trend, retaining newcomers remains a challenge, contributing to growing labour shortages and increasing pressure to attract and integrate a skilled workforce.

The main transition challenge relates to socio-economic and demographic transition, and more specifically in relation to the RUSTIK Living Lab experiment to immigrant retention.

Policy focus

The DRP pilot focused on **the effects of Finland's 2025 Integration Act reform** (Integration Act 681/2023) **on municipal integration services in North Karelia**. The reform reorganises the integration system by transferring substantial responsibilities from the state to municipalities and extending their mandate to include all immigrant groups. It aims to promote earlier and more effective integration, improve access to services (particularly for those outside the labour force), and enhance the quality of language training, while promoting equality, non-discrimination and stronger multi-sectoral cooperation. For many municipalities, this represents a significant shift, as they are now responsible for providing integration services for the first time under the new legislation.

The reform coincides with the transfer of employment services to municipalities under the Act on the Organisation of Employment Services, concentrating both integration and employment responsibilities at the municipal level. However, in regions, such as North Karelia, employment services are organised regionally by the Employment Area rather than by individual municipalities.

Rationale, objectives and scope

The objective of the DRP pilot is to **assess how municipalities in North Karelia are coping with the implementation and requirements of the 2025 Integration Act reform**. Specifically, the pilot assesses:

1. the measures municipalities have taken to comply with the requirements of the reformed Act.
2. implementation coherence across different municipalities.
3. the relevance of the reform in relation to municipalities' needs, challenges, and resources; and
4. issues of equality, considering both the differing capacities of municipalities to implement the Act and the varying opportunities for immigrants to access and benefit from integration services.

The Integration Act reform entered into force on 1 January 2025, as such the DRP is an ex-post assessment of the Act's effects on municipal integration services in North Karelia.

Actors and methods

The DRP process was managed by the Pilot Region partner, Regional Council of North Karelia. The Pilot Region partner was responsible for the organisation, implementation and coordination of the process.

A key partner was the then-called Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment, the regional state authority responsible for steering, coordination, and overseeing integration policy. Within the DRP, its role was to use the findings to improve its steering and coordination practices and to report results to the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment.

The main focus of the DRP was to assess how municipalities perceive the new law and how they are managing its implementation. Six practical guiding questions were selected:

Process of law implementation

1. What kinds of changes has the law reform brought to the organisation of municipal integration services?

Resources for law implementation

2. Do municipalities have sufficient resources to provide integration services as required by the law?
Coherence of implementation of law
3. Do municipalities implement the law consistently across municipalities?

Relevance of the law

4. Do municipalities consider the law to be relevant in light of their integration-related needs and challenges?

Equality

5. Do rural municipalities consider the law reform to be fair?
6. Are municipal integration services equally accessible to different immigrant groups?

The DRP consisted of 11 semi-structured interviews with municipal integration coordinators (in some municipalities, municipal employment officials also participated in the interviews), a reflection workshop with migration specialists from the Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment to validate and further elaborate on selected findings from the municipal interviews, and a web-based Immigrant Integration Survey (developed as part of the RUSTIK Living Lab process). The survey collected data from immigrants living in North Karelia providing insights into municipal integration services from the perspective of service users.

Additional data sources included the Finnish Ministry of Justice's official online database for legislation and legal information (Finlex) and other public websites on the law reform. No significant data gaps were identified.

Key findings

Key findings from the DRP

Inconsistent implementation and unclear roles: Implementation of the Integration Act varies significantly across municipalities, reflecting different levels of experience and interpretations of responsibilities. This leads to uneven service quality (from basic advice to holistic support), unclear mandates for integration coordinators, and ambiguity regarding the scope, duration, and target groups of services. Limited operational guidance further contributes to inconsistent practices.

Gaps in service focus and coordination: Integration services primarily target refugees, with less attention to other immigrant groups. At the same time, unclear division of responsibilities, and

limited coordination and data sharing with the employment authorities, and insufficient cultural competence in mainstream services increase workloads and reduce effectiveness.

Alignment with rural contexts

Strengths in rural settings: The Act provides a strong foundation for legitimising integration services and extending the coverage to all immigrant groups. Smaller municipalities benefit from close relationships enabling personalised, trust-based support and effective local cooperation.

Structural challenges: Rural areas face constraints, including limited municipal level presence of employment authorities, reducing opportunities for interaction and continuity of support. Separate responsibilities, limited data access, and non-interoperable information systems hinder integrated service provision. Outreach is often limited to jobseekers, and multilingual civic orientation is difficult to deliver due to small and diverse populations.

Resource allocation and participation of rural actors

Unequal financing model: Lump-sum compensation covers only certain groups despite municipalities' responsibility for all immigrants, creating resource disparities.

Disadvantages for remote municipalities and future risks: The funding model does not reflect higher rural service costs (e.g. long travel distances), and the removal of cost-based reimbursements has widened inequalities. Current funding is temporarily supported by Ukrainian arrivals, but long-term financial sustainability is uncertain.

Future considerations

Need for flexibility and clearer guidance: Municipalities call for greater discretion in service provision, more flexible integration timelines, clearer role definition, and improved data sharing. Integrating multilingual civic orientation into mandatory training was also suggested.

Capacity-building effect of the DRP: The process increased awareness and understanding among coordinators, helping identify overlooked responsibilities (e.g. promoting good community relations) and supporting mutual learning.

6.7 DRP Fiche – Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin

Regional context and transition challenge

The Decentralised Rural Proofing (DRP) covered three municipalities with different socio-economic and demographic profiles, which are jointly covered by a Local Action Group (LAG).

The region is undergoing socio-economic and demographic transition. In this context, there is potential to strengthen the capacity of local communities, particularly farmers, food producers and processors, to use agricultural production as a resource for territorial development. This implies a shift from an export-oriented model centred on primary production towards more

endogenous forms of development based on local processing, cooperation between actors, and the retention of added value within the territory.

Policy focus

The DRP was conducted bottom-up. It was not part of a policy process and was not linked to a single policy. This was because multiple policies relate to food production and utilisation, namely:

- Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and its application in the region in the form of direct area payments for agricultural activities and related support (CAP Pillar I - agriculture);
- Local development strategy of Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin - a bases for drawing funding from LEADER/CLLD (CAP Pillar II - rural development)
- European food quality schemes (geographical identifications and quality schemes)
- Municipal policies for the organisation of food festivals (rural development)

Figure 10: Policy mix addressing food in rural areas of Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin

Within this policy mix, the DRP focused on specific issues as described in the following section.

Rationale, objectives and scope

The DRP built on the focus established through the Living Lab experiment on how food can support a transition from export-oriented production to more endogenous development based on local processing and cooperation. In line with the bottom-up approach, the rationale was to engage stakeholders in a dialogue that could reveal whether local food is perceived as an asset for territorial development and how rural policies may need to adapt.

It focused on **three key objectives**: (1) gain overview of the regional food production potential and support through CAP Pillar I (2) review the role of LEADER/CLLD and quality schemes to encourage cooperation within local agri-food chains and (3) review the extent to which local food is promoted through municipal food policies and in particular festivals.

Actors and methods

The DRP process brought together a community of actors from the three neighbouring municipalities (academic, NGO, business, citizens). Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski led the analytical work by identifying and integrating data sources, developing a GIS-based tool, preparing interim analyses, and defining stakeholder profiles. The LAG Secretariat led stakeholder engagement and data collection by coordinating workshops and interviews, updating information from official registers, providing additional data for the GIS, and gathering information on the fifteen food-related projects funded under the Local Development Strategy (LDS) through an

online questionnaire. Results of the DRP pilon will be discussed with the mayors of the two municipalities.

The DRP included a mix of methods and proofing questions outlined in Table 11 and categorised per objective.

Table 13: Troyan-Apriltsi-Ugarchin DRP objectives, methods and proofing questions

Objective	Questions for proofing	Involved actors	Methods
To gain an overview of the regional food production potential including overview of producers and their produce.	Who are the agri-food actors? What do they produce? What are their plans for the future? Which actors remain invisible to policymakers? What are the existing informal practices?	LAG Farmers SMEs	Interviews and workshop with farmers; <i>supported by Geographical Information System (GIS) On the way of local food in TAU'</i>
To review the extent to which LEADER/CLLD and quality schemes promote cooperation around local agri-food chains.	What types of actors are beneficiaries of the Local Development Strategy (LDS) and quality schemes? What type of activities have received support (agricultural or food processing)? How does the LDS promote cooperation between actors? What is the administrative burden on beneficiaries when applying for funding through LEADER/CLLD? What types of projects have <i>not</i> been approved for funding through LEADER/CLLD? Do quality schemes promote local agri-food networks? What quality labels are being obtained? How do they add value to the territory and to producers?	LAG Farmers SMEs	Standardised online questionnaire. Interviews with SMEs farmers, and LAG employees.
To examine the contribution of food festivals to territorial development, and territorial branding.	What is the profile of festival participants? Do they sell own or purchased products? How local foods are promoted? What benefits do food festivals bring to the agri-food chain?	Municipal authorities (festival organisers) Farmers SMEs	Workshop with farmers; Interviews with farmers; Observations of festivals

Key findings

Food production potential in the region and support through CAP Pillar 1

The region is home to a significant number of enterprises. Approximately 10 per cent of all enterprises receive support through CAP Pillar I direct payments. These are food-processing enterprises that also engage in primary agricultural production. Most are micro and small family-

owned businesses. The agri-food sector is undergoing a gradual transition, with some actors shifting from primary production towards food processing activities. The decline in the number of farms is mainly due to the increasing number of legislative requirements related to animal husbandry, along with demographic changes. The gender breakdown shows that the majority of registered farms receiving support through CAP Pillar I are led by men (see Figure 11)

Figure 11: Number of registered farmers receiving support through CAP Pillar 1

Under this objective, the DRP revealed:

- **unequal access:** agri-food actors who are not covered through CAP Pillar 1 include (1) small farms that are not registered as agricultural producers; (2) farmers who cultivate less than 5 hectares of arable land; (3) farmers who cultivate diverse crops, each of which covers less than 5 hectares (characteristic to organic producers).
- **ineffective participatory processes:** there is a lack of established procedures that track how stakeholders' input provided during local consultations is utilised in strategies.
- **bureaucratic burden and institutional distrust:** large amounts of paperwork discourage agri-food actors from seeking financial support from public bodies. Additionally, stakeholders share concerns that inspections may be subject to corruption.
- **regulatory burden:** establishing small processing facilities requires meeting high number of regulatory requirements.
- **gaps in support across the agri-food value chain:** support measures are primarily targeted at agricultural production, while downstream activities such as processing, marketing, distribution, and communication with consumers are only partially covered or require access to separate measures.

Support through LEADER/CLLD and quality schemes for cooperation in local agri-food chains

Under this objective, the DRP revealed:

- **excessive documentation requirements:** a minimum of 55 and a maximum of 74 documents required when putting forward a project application under the Local Development Strategy. Smaller farmers are with lowest capacity to fulfil complex application procedures.

- **cooperation between agri-food actors** is supported primarily when it is formalised and documented, as policy monitoring and accountability rely on verifiable written evidence. Informal but effective forms of cooperation may remain unrecognised.

Food festivals as tools for food promotion and broader territorial development

Under this objective, the DRP revealed:

- **participatory design and outreach:** municipalities lack data-based approach to maintaining contact with farmers and food producers for the organisation of festivals. No formal or informal consultation groups such as 'food councils' exist to support the organisation of festivals.
- the **effectiveness of festivals** as a tool for food promotion is hindered by the lack of clear criteria for farmers to participate.
- **functional rural-urban system:** there is a connection between rural and urban areas, especially in terms of tourism, consumption and knowledge sharing. The development of rural and urban areas, however, continues to be largely managed by separate administrative structures and policies. There is significant potential to strengthen rural-urban linkages through the food system.

Implications for future

- The DRP confirms the policy adaptation pathways identified in the Living Lab experiment, which points towards a transition from sectoral policy approaches to a more holistic territorial logic combined with strengthened territorial governance.
- From a methodological perspective, DRP can function as a bottom-up process when there is strong cooperation between researchers, intermediaries, and local stakeholders; available data to formulate and test ideas; and a flexible process format.
- Rather than starting from a specific policy, the strength of the approach lies in focusing on a concrete area of social and economic life. This allows stakeholders to articulate needs and experiences from their own perspective before examining how existing policies support, overlook, or constrain them.

